

The Cost of Care, the Weight of Norms

A Cross-Sectional and Experimental Study on Maternal Employment in Kosovo

MASTER'S THESIS

by

Diellza Veliu

*Eberhard Karls University of Tübingen
Master of Public Policy and Social Change*

Supervisors:

Prof. Dr. Pia Schober

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Abstract

This thesis investigates how childcare accessibility and social norms shape maternal employment in Kosovo, a country with low female labor force participation and limited Early Childhood Education and Care (ECEC) provision. Primary data were collected through a mixed-method survey design, combining a cross-sectional questionnaire of parents with at least one child under six (N = 241) and a factorial survey experiment (N = 710 vignette evaluations). Logistic regression, KHB decomposition, and interaction models test affordability, availability, and quality as predictors of maternal employment, with social norms as mediators and partner support and relative income as moderators. Mixed-effects models analyze the factorial experiment.

Findings show that childcare affordability is the decisive barrier: mothers perceiving care as unaffordable were significantly less likely to be employed, while availability and quality had no independent effects. Mediation analyses revealed that neither descriptive nor prescriptive norms explained this link, underscoring affordability as a structural constraint. Partner support correlated with higher baseline employment but did not moderate the relationship between affordability and employment. By contrast, relative income significantly conditioned the effect: affordability mattered most for financially dependent women, but little for primary earners. The factorial experiment further demonstrated that normative approval of maternal employment was context-dependent, increasing for older children, flexible jobs, supportive partners, and subsidized childcare.

Keywords: Maternal employment, ECEC, social norms, partner support, Kosovo

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1 Introduction

Maternal employment stands at the intersection of gender equality and social policy in the 21st century. Across Europe, the expansion of Early Childhood Education and Care (ECEC) has been celebrated as a hallmark of the “social investment” turn: childcare is no longer viewed merely as a private arrangement but as a dual investment in women’s economic independence and children’s development (European Commission, 2022; Klenk & Reiter, 2023). Universal access to affordable, high-quality childcare has enabled high female employment rates in Nordic welfare states, where ECEC has long been institutionalized as a public good (Lind, 2021; OECD Family Database, 2023). Yet such opportunities remain deeply uneven across countries. In low-income, liberal, and post-socialist contexts, mothers of young children continue to face a dual burden: limited or costly childcare services on one hand, and strong normative expectations of maternal caregiving on the other (Addati et al., 2022; OECD, 2023).

Kosovo represents a particularly stark case of this paradox. Despite rising levels of female education and formal policy commitments to gender equality, women’s labor force participation remains among the lowest in Europe. Fewer than one in five women are employed, and childcare coverage is extremely limited, only around 11 percent of children under five are enrolled in early education (ASK, 2024; Gjelaj, Rraci & Bajrami, 2018; Demas et al., 2021). Public childcare is scarce, underfunded, and concentrated in urban centers, leaving most families dependent on costly private provision or informal care (Mustafa, 2021; Behrami et al., 2020). At the same time, deeply embedded cultural expectations continue to cast mothers as primary caregivers, reinforcing women’s withdrawal from paid work after childbirth. This raises the central research problem of this thesis: why, despite higher education and policy aspirations, do Kosovar mothers remain systematically excluded from employment?

While existing scholarship explains how childcare policies support maternal employment in high-coverage welfare states, far less is known about their dynamics in low-income, post-socialist settings such as Kosovo. Comparative research has largely centered on advanced welfare regimes, leaving a critical blind spot in understanding how the three dimensions of childcare accessibility (affordability, availability, and quality) interact with cultural attitudes and household dynamics in under-researched regions, and under what conditions such policies succeed or fail.

This thesis addresses these gaps by generating original survey-based evidence from Kosovo, integrating structural and cultural perspectives, and applying an innovative factorial survey experiment. In doing so, it extends debates on childcare and maternal employment beyond high-income welfare states

The analysis is guided by two research questions:

1. *How does childcare accessibility affect women's labor market participation in Kosovo, and to what extent do social norms mediate this relationship?*
2. *How do variations in childcare affordability, job flexibility, partner support, and child's age affect public support for a mother's decision to return to work?*

Together, these questions enable a nuanced examination of both structural and normative mechanisms, and of the conditions under which maternal employment is socially enabled or discouraged.

The thesis proceeds as follows. Chapter 2 reviews existing research on childcare policies, maternal employment, and social norms, situating the Kosovo case within broader comparative debates. Chapter 3 develops the conceptual framework and hypotheses. Chapter 4 analyzes the institutional and policy context of childcare in Kosovo. Chapter 5 outlines the methodology and data sources. Chapter 6 presents descriptive findings. Chapter 7 reports the results from multivariate regressions and the factorial survey experiment. Finally, the discussion and conclusion reflect on the theoretical, empirical, and policy implications of the findings, and identify avenues for future research.

2 Literature Review and Previous Studies

A substantial body of research shows that expanding public childcare availability can increase maternal employment, though effects vary depending on context and design. Brilli et al. (2016), using variation in childcare availability across Italian municipalities, estimate that a 10-percentage point increase in childcare coverage raises mothers' probability of employment by about 13 percentage points, with stronger effects in provinces where availability is scarce. Similarly, Bauernschuster and Schlotter (2015) exploit the 1996 German childcare reform in a quasi-experimental design. They find that eligibility for public childcare increased maternal employment by around 6 percentage points, with a 10-percentage point rise in childcare coverage leading to a 3.7 percentage point increase in employment. The effects were particularly pronounced for mothers of young children, especially single mothers. Yet childcare availability does not translate into uniform employment effects across mothers. Zoch and Hondralis (2017), combining German SOEP panel data with county-level administrative coverage rates, to examine returns to work after childbirth. They show that expanded low-cost, state-subsidized childcare shortened mothers' employment interruptions and increased the likelihood of returning to substantial (part or full-time) rather than marginal employment. However, these effects were statistically significant only for West German mothers and primarily after a second birth.

A similar pattern of heterogeneous responses emerges when turning from availability to affordability. Evidence from New Zealand's "20 hours free" early childhood education reform, analyzed by Bouchard, Cheung, and Pacheco (2021) using administrative difference-in-differences data, reveals heterogeneous effects: mothers with two eligible children increased their labor force participation, while some single-child mothers reduced employment, possibly due to income effects. This illustrates that affordability matters most for lower-income households. Beyond costs, childcare quality is also critical. Schober and Spiess (2015), linking SOEP data with regional indicators of group size, staff-child ratios, and staff qualifications, find that quality mattered primarily for mothers of toddlers in East Germany. In particular, each additional child per group reduced mothers' employment probability by 6 percentage points, and smaller groups were associated with longer working hours. By contrast, no effects emerged in West Germany or for mothers with preschool-aged children. These findings highlight that the employment effects of childcare quality are strongest where childcare use is culturally normalized.

However, the effectiveness of childcare expansion is far from universal. Evidence from post-socialist countries illustrates these limitations. Lovász (2016) notes that despite policy efforts to expand subsidized childcare in Central and Eastern Europe, maternal employment often remains low. The reasons lie less in coverage alone and more in interacting institutional and cultural constraints: extremely long or poorly paid parental leaves, inflexible labor markets with few part-time opportunities, and persistent maternalism gender norms rooted in the socialist legacy. Even quasi-experimental evidence from Hungary shows that while access to childcare at age three explains part of mothers' re-entry into work, much of the increase is driven by parental leave policies and social expectations rather than childcare per se. This highlights that structural reforms cannot be disentangled from cultural attitudes, making social norms a crucial factor in understanding maternal employment.

Therefore, a *second layer* of empirical inquiry emphasizes the role of gendered social norms in shaping whether mothers take up employment after childbirth. Andringa, Nieuwenhuis, and van Gerven (2015) provide one of the most robust comparative analyses by combining European Social Survey data with multilevel models across 23 European countries. Their study examines how women's working hours are shaped by the interplay between gender role attitudes, motherhood, and country-level contexts of public childcare expenditure and prevailing gender norms. They find that mothers and women with traditional attitudes work fewer hours, but that the motherhood penalty is smaller in countries with extensive childcare provision and, to a lesser extent, in more egalitarian normative contexts. Importantly, childcare support was especially effective in sustaining the working hours of mothers with traditional attitudes, suggesting that services may buffer rather than widen normative divides. While previous studies largely document associations between gender norms and maternal employment, Moriconi and Rodríguez-Planas (2021) address the causality problem directly. Using reproductive health liberalization laws in the "grandmothers' generation" as an instrument for local gender norms, they show that progressive attitudes substantially mitigate the motherhood employment penalty. In their preferred specification, a one standard deviation increase in non-traditional norms increases maternal employment by 5.6 percentage points, equivalent to cutting the average motherhood employment gap by almost half. Importantly, no comparable effect is found for men, underscoring that the mechanism operates specifically through motherhood.

Experimental approaches add further nuance. Hermes et al. (2024) conduct a randomized information experiment with mothers of young children in Germany, correcting their misperceptions about prevailing gender norms. Most mothers overestimated how conservative their social environment was; when informed that local norms were in fact more liberal, mothers updated their perceptions, adopted more progressive attitudes toward maternal employment, and reported higher intentions to increase their working hours. Importantly, these effects were concentrated among mothers with supportive conditions, such as access to childcare and partner involvement. Finally, similar dynamics are evident beyond Europe. Ruppanner et al. (2021), analyzing U.S. data, find that high childcare costs particularly depress maternal employment among less-educated mothers, whereas for college-educated mothers, costs are only consequential in states with traditional gender norms.

The third strand of literature highlights the significance of intra-household decision-making and support in enabling maternal employment. Even when childcare services are accessible and social norms begin to shift, mothers' actual labor market behavior often hinges on negotiations within the household. Bröckel (2016), using German SOEP panel data, demonstrates that both instrumental and emotional partner support substantially increase women's likelihood of re-entering employment after childbirth. An egalitarian division of childcare and housework, or partners reducing their own working hours, strongly predicts women's return, particularly to full-time work. Emotional encouragement also plays a role, especially in highly educated couples. When men's prenatal resources outweigh women's, mothers are less likely to return. This underscores the importance of relative bargaining power. While the reliance on self-reported support introduces subjectivity, the study highlights that intra-household negotiations are as crucial as institutional childcare provision in shaping maternal employment trajectories. Extending this perspective cross-nationally, Dotti Sani and Scherer (2017) show that the salience of household resources is context-dependent: in weaker-support regimes such as Italy and Germany, partner support and household characteristics weigh heavily on maternal employment decisions, whereas in Norway, generous childcare and family policies largely overshadow intra-household constraints. Recent work complicates this picture. Ingenfeld (2021), using British Household Panel Survey data and structural equation modeling, argues that the apparent benefits of paternal involvement may be overstated. Career-oriented women are more likely to select into egalitarian partnerships, making it difficult to separate genuine causal effects from selection bias. Once this is addressed,

partner involvement emerges as less influential overall, except among disadvantaged mothers (low education, low income), for whom paternal engagement remains critical. This finding tempers earlier claims, suggesting that while partner support matters, its effect is uneven and contingent on women's socioeconomic position. Taken together with earlier studies, these findings suggest that no single mechanism, whether childcare provision, social norms, or household support, fully explains variation in maternal employment. This recognition sets the stage for a broader synthesis.

Yet despite this progress in identifying multiple drivers, important blind spots remain. First, most studies derive from high-income welfare states with established childcare systems, meaning that findings often reflect conditions of institutional abundance rather than scarcity. While a few recent studies from Southern Europe (e.g., Italy) offer somewhat closer parallels to contexts of weaker welfare provision, the bulk of research remains anchored in Western, high-income settings. As a result, we know far less about how these mechanisms operate in environments where childcare infrastructure is underdeveloped, labor markets are fragile, and households face acute financial constraints. Second, much of the existing work continues to isolate single mechanisms, such as availability, affordability, quality, or norms, rather than examining how these factors reinforce or counteract one another in practice. Third, the field remains methodologically skewed: observational and quasi-experimental studies dominate, while innovative approaches that can capture causal mechanisms more directly (such as experimental vignette designs) are still rare and heavily concentrated in Western Europe.

Kosovo provides a critical opportunity to address these blind spots. As a post-conflict, lower-income society with one of the scarcest childcare systems in Europe, high costs relative to income, and deeply entrenched maternalist norms, Kosovo represents not just a neglected case but a crucial "hard test" for existing theories. By investigating how structural constraints, normative pressures, and household dynamics jointly shape maternal employment under such conditions, this thesis contributes in two ways: empirically, by generating original evidence from a setting largely absent in comparative research; and theoretically, by probing the scope conditions of mechanisms identified in high-income contexts to determine whether they hold or unravel under conditions of institutional scarcity and cultural constraint.

3 Conceptual Framework and Hypotheses

This chapter develops a conceptual framework linking childcare accessibility to maternal employment in Kosovo. It argues that institutional provision alone is insufficient: social norms may mediate whether childcare access translates into maternal employment, while intra-household factors such as partner support and relative income moderate this relationship. On this basis, the chapter formulates hypotheses for both the cross-sectional and factorial survey components.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

3.1 Determinants of Maternal Employment

Childcare Accessibility and Maternal Employment. Drawing on Rational Choice Theory (Becker, 1976), maternal employment is conceptualized as a utility-maximizing decision. Women are assumed to weigh the expected costs and benefits of entering or remaining in the labor force. In this framework, childcare-related constraints, such as limited access, high costs, or poor perceived quality, constitute important *opportunity costs*, especially for mothers of young children. When accessible, affordable, and high-quality childcare is available, the cost of maternal employment is reduced, making labor force participation a more rational and viable option. In addition, Role Conflict Theory (Greenhaus & Beutell, 1985) emphasizes the psychological tension between work and caregiving roles. When childcare is perceived as safe and developmentally enriching, this conflict is reduced.

Childcare accessibility is conceptualized along the three OECD dimensions:

- Availability refers to the perceived presence and accessibility of formal childcare services in a respondent's local area.
- Affordability refers to the perceived and actual financial burden of childcare relative to a household's income.
- Quality refers to the perceived standard and developmental value of formal childcare services.

In this study, childcare accessibility is measured in two complementary ways: reported usage data (e.g., enrollment, hours, satisfaction with care) and perceived accessibility (availability, affordability, and quality). Reported indicators are primarily used descriptively to contextualize childcare patterns, while perceptions provide the analytical basis for hypothesis testing. Detailed survey items and measurement procedures are described in Chapter 5 (Methodology).

This leads to the first hypothesis derived from the framework:

***Hypothesis 1:** Mothers who perceive childcare services in their area as accessible (in terms of availability, affordability, and quality) are more likely to be employed than those who perceive childcare as inaccessible.*

Social Norms as a Mediator. Social norms, defined as shared behavioral expectations within a community, are introduced as a mediating mechanism to explain how and why childcare access may or may not lead to women's labor force participation. In line with recent scholarship, this study avoids treating culture as a static background factor. Instead, social norms are conceptualized as dynamic, context-dependent psychological mechanisms that shape behavior by embedding it in webs of interdependence and expectations (Bicchieri, 2017).

Building on Bicchieri's theory of social norms in interdependent decision-making contexts, the framework distinguishes between two analytically distinct but complementary types of norms:

- *Descriptive norms* refer to individuals' empirical expectations, beliefs about what others in their reference group typically do.
- *Prescriptive (or injunctive) norms* refer to normative expectations, beliefs about what others think one ought to do, including anticipated rewards or sanctions for compliance or deviance.

According to Bicchieri (2017), for a social norm to influence behavior, three conditions must be met: (1) individuals must recognize a rule of behavior; (2) they must have conditional preferences to conform; and (3) they must hold both empirical and normative expectations about others' behaviors and attitudes. These dynamics are especially salient in transitional societies like Kosovo, where gender equality reforms coexist with entrenched traditional norms.

For example, descriptive norms may suggest 'Most mothers with young children stay home,' while prescriptive norms signal 'Mothers should stay home with young children. When these expectations align with traditional gender ideologies, they may act as powerful constraints on women's labor force participation, regardless of whether accessible, affordable, and high-quality childcare is available. Thus, even when institutional supports such as ECEC services are in place, prevailing social norms can significantly condition whether mothers feel permitted or expected to make use of these services. In this way, social norms mediate the effect of structural childcare accessibility on maternal employment outcomes.

Accordingly, the following hypotheses are proposed:

***Hypothesis H2a:** The effect of perceived childcare accessibility on maternal employment is partially mediated by respondents' empirical expectations about what others in their community typically do.*

***Hypothesis H2b:** The effect of perceived childcare accessibility on maternal employment is partially mediated by respondents' normative expectations about what others in their community believe mothers should do.*

Partner Support as a Moderator. In this framework, partner support is conceptualized as a moderating variable that conditions the relationship between perceived childcare accessibility (availability, affordability, and quality) and maternal employment. Drawing on Work-Family Enrichment Theory (Greenhaus & Powell, 2006), partner support is understood as a source of cross-domain enrichment, whereby resources and experiences from the family domain enhance functioning in the work domain. The theory distinguishes between two pathways: the instrumental pathway, referring to tangible support such as shared childcare duties or domestic labor; and the affective pathway, which includes emotional encouragement, validation, and alignment with the mother's employment aspirations.

When partners actively participate in caregiving and household tasks (instrumental support), mothers are more likely to experience reduced time constraints, less role overload, and greater flexibility, making workforce (re)entry more feasible. Simultaneously, emotional support, such as encouragement to pursue a career or reassurance in using formal childcare, can strengthen maternal confidence and reduce internalized or external normative pressures. Thus, partner support amplifies the enabling effects of childcare services by addressing constraints that persist within the private sphere of the household. This approach also draws on the second half of the gender revolution framework (Goldscheider et al., 2015), which emphasizes that institutional progress toward gender equality must be accompanied by transformations in men's domestic roles. Without adequate partner engagement in care and household responsibilities, even high-quality formal childcare may not suffice to shift maternal employment outcomes.

***Hypothesis 3:** The positive association between perceived childcare accessibility (availability, affordability, and quality) and maternal employment is stronger when women report high levels of A) emotional and B) instrumental support from their partners.*

Relative Income as a Moderator. Relative income, defined as the mother's earnings in proportion to her partner's, is conceptualized as a moderating variable that conditions the relationship between perceived childcare accessibility and maternal employment. The theoretical foundation for this mechanism lies in bargaining models of intra-household decision-making (Lundberg & Pollak, 1996), which argue that household choices reflect the relative preferences and power of individual members rather than a unified household utility function. In these models, economic resources, particularly individual income, serve as bargaining assets that shape individuals' ability to influence domestic arrangements. Women who contribute a larger share of household income typically hold greater bargaining power, enabling them to assert preferences regarding employment, childcare usage, and the division of unpaid labor.

In the context of Kosovo, where patriarchal gender norms may constrain women's decision-making autonomy, this economic leverage is especially consequential. Even when childcare services are perceived as accessible, mothers with low relative income may lack the household authority to act on those opportunities. By contrast, women with higher relative earnings are better positioned to negotiate the use of formal childcare and reduce potential resistance from partners or extended family regarding their employment decisions.

Hypothesis 4: *The negative effect of unaffordable childcare on maternal employment is stronger among mothers with lower relative income shares, whereas mothers with higher income shares are less affected by affordability constraints.*

3.2 Testing Normative Expectations through a Factorial Survey

The cross-sectional survey provides insights into how childcare accessibility, social norms, and household dynamics are associated with maternal employment. Yet, it cannot capture how societal expectations shift under systematically varied conditions. To address this limitation, the study employs a factorial survey experiment (FSE). Drawing on Bicchieri's (2017) theory of social norms, the FSE focuses on injunctive norms, beliefs about what mothers ought to do in different structural and family contexts. Unlike correlational approaches, factorial surveys enable causal inference by embedding variation directly into hypothetical scenarios. This makes it possible to observe how public expectations change depending on contextual factors such as the child's age, partner involvement, job flexibility, and childcare affordability. By analyzing judgments across these experimentally varied conditions, the study isolates the mechanisms through which social and structural constraints translate into normative expectations about maternal employment. In addition to advancing theory, the design incorporates a policy-relevant dimension: a vignette reflecting the Prishtina childcare subsidy. Embedding this initiative into the experiment provides original evidence on how such measures are perceived by the public and whether they foster broader societal support for maternal labor force participation, an issue that has not been addressed in prior research.

Justification for Selected Dimensions. While partner support and childcare affordability are already conceptually and empirically discussed in earlier sections, the paragraphs below explain the rationale behind the two remaining dimensions: child's age and job flexibility.

Child's age: The age categories (1 year and 5 years) mark two crucial transition points in the institutional and cultural expectations surrounding maternal care. The age of 1 year was chosen because it typically marks the end of the maternity leave period in Kosovo (12 months of job-protected leave), when many mothers face pressure to return to work despite limited childcare options for infants. In contrast, 5 years corresponds to the age at which children enter preparatory

classes prior to starting primary school at age six. By that age, early formal education is widely accepted and even expected, reducing the perceived need for maternal full-time presence at home. This contrast allows the vignette design to assess how public expectations of maternal employment shift as the child transitions from infancy to early schooling. This distinction is empirically grounded, as prior factorial survey research has shown that a child's age is a key determinant of attitudes toward maternal employment. For example, Frodermann, Hipp, and Bünning (2024) find that support for maternal employment is significantly lower when the child is one year old compared to three, while Zangger et al. (2021) shows that support for part-time work increases as the youngest child grows older.

Job flexibility: This dimension captures structural conditions that influence societal expectations of maternal employment, particularly how women balance paid work with caregiving responsibilities. The rationale is twofold: *Alignment with structural feasibility:* Empirical research has demonstrated that jobs offering higher levels of schedule autonomy such as flextime or teleworking are perceived as more compatible with family responsibilities. In contrast, rigid or non-standard schedules are viewed as less manageable, especially for mothers of young children. For example, a UK study finds that mothers with access to flextime and teleworking are significantly less likely to reduce their working hours after childbirth, while those lacking such flexibility face higher discontinuation rates (Chung & van der Horst, 2018). *Normative expectations reflect feasibility:* Public judgments about whether a mother *should* return to work are conditioned not just by her desire or need, but also by the perceived structure of the job. A flexible schedule often signals that maternal responsibilities can be managed without sacrificing caregiving norms or child well-being.

Based on this vignette design, the following hypothesis is proposed:

Hypothesis 5 (Factorial Survey Hypothesis): Respondents' normative expectations regarding maternal employment and childcare usage are shaped by four contextual dimensions.

- H5a: Support is lower when the child is younger (1 vs. 5 years old).
- H5b: Support is higher when the partner provides strong instrumental support.
- H5c: Support is higher when the job is more flexible (e.g., remote).
- H5d: Support is higher when childcare is more affordable i.e., the cost is lower relative to income and a subsidy is available.

4 The Kosovo Context: Policy, Institutions, and Norms

4.1 From UNMIK Residualism to Post-Independence Market Familialism

Kosovo's welfare trajectory has been shaped by two critical phases: the UNMIK administration after 1999 and the post-independence period after 2008. Together, these phases established a liberal, market-oriented model that left childcare and family policy at the margins.

Under UNMIK, Kosovo experienced what scholars describe as the most radical departure from socialism among post-Yugoslav states (Mustafa, 2021). With no domestic institutions in place, international actors such as the World Bank, IMF, and EU designed a minimalist welfare regime from scratch. This system was defined by a narrow social protection floor financed through general taxation, with the state retreating from its role as provider and shifting care responsibilities to families and markets. In Esping-Andersen's terms, Kosovo was steered toward a liberal welfare model: residual, means-tested, and reliant on self-reliance and market provision. Within this framework, Early Childhood Education and Care (ECEC) received little attention. Policy priorities were oriented toward macroeconomic stabilization, privatization, and institution-building, leaving family policy absent and childcare relegated to a marginal concern. This early neglect created a path dependency that continues to constrain provision today.

After independence in 2008, Kosovo's welfare state evolved in a fragmented, path-dependent manner. Governments layered new benefits onto the residual structure established under UNMIK, often in ad hoc and politically selective ways. The result has been the consolidation of what scholars call *market familialism*: families remain the main providers of care, while childcare services are dominated by market solutions (Mustafa, 2021; Bartlett & Uvalić, 2022).

More recently, pressures of Europeanisation have introduced a modest but important countercurrent. Through participation in EU Economic Reform Programmes and aspirations for membership, Kosovo has been encouraged to adopt EU-aligned standards in work-family reconciliation and social inclusion (Dobrotić, 2022).

4.2 The Legal and Policy Framework of Early Childhood Education and Care in Kosovo

A particularly notable outcome of these Europeanisation pressures has been the reform of Kosovo's legal and strategic framework governing Early Childhood Education and Care (ECEC). The

outdated 2006 Law on Preschool Education (Law No. 02/L-52), which narrowly focused on ages 3-6, has been replaced by the comprehensive 2023 Law on Early Childhood Education (Law No. 08/L-153). This new law represents a shift toward an integrated, rights-based, and developmental approach to early childhood, covering children from 0 to 6 years old and establishing clear standards for quality, inclusiveness, decentralization, and multi-provider models aligned with EU principles.

Under the new framework, ECEC is the first level of the education system, divided into nurseries (ages 9 months to 3 years), kindergartens (ages 3-6), and the now compulsory preparatory class (ages 5-6), marking a key step toward alignment with international standards. Services may be provided through public, private, community-based, or public-private partnership models, with municipalities responsible for planning, financing, and monitoring, reflecting Kosovo's decentralized governance model.

This legal overhaul aligns closely with Kosovo's Education Strategy 2022-2026, which places ECEC as its highest strategic priority under the objective to "Increase Inclusion and Equal Access." The strategy emphasizes infrastructure expansion, quality assurance, intersectoral coordination, and raising public awareness. Although symbolically significant, actual implementation has been uneven. The national ECEC curriculum was only approved in 2023 and piloted in 2024, following substantial delays from institutional instability. Meanwhile, other objectives such as inclusive infrastructure, integrated cross-sectoral services, and promoting gender equality in the ECEC workforce remain largely unrealized.

Taken together, these developments illustrate a dual reality: Kosovo has made visible strides in formalizing its ECEC policy framework, yet substantial gaps persist in implementation. This contrast underscores deeper structural constraints, revealing how Europeanisation remains more rhetorical than institutionalized in practice.

4.3. The Implementation Gap: Realities of ECEC Provision in Kosovo

While policy reforms signal alignment with European standards, actual provision tells a different story. By 2024, Kosovo operated only 62 public centers, a modest rise from 44 in 2019, far short of the Ministry of Education, Science, Technology, and Innovation's (MESTI) goal of establishing

160 new institutions by 2025. This stark discrepancy underscores the extent of resource and institutional constraints hindering ECEC expansion.

While private provision has seen more visible growth, rising to 175 licensed centers by 2025, significant regulatory challenges remain. A 2019 World Bank analysis revealed that more than 250 private ECEC providers operated without licenses, posing substantial risks regarding child safety, educational quality, and equity (Demas et al., 2021). Such informal provision contributes to data inaccuracies, complicating effective oversight and planning.

The inadequacy of ECEC coverage becomes even clearer when enrollment is juxtaposed with actual population needs. According to data from the Kosovo Agency of Statistics (hereafter: ASK, 2024), only approximately 15,074 children aged 0-5 were enrolled in formal ECEC (excluding the preparatory class), representing just 11.4% of approximately 132,000 children in this age bracket, far below international benchmarks. For children under age three, the situation is even more alarming, with enrollment at only 9.9% (4,356 out of roughly 44,000), starkly lower than the EU’s Barcelona 2030 target of 45% (Council of the European Union, 2022).

The issue persists even within compulsory preparatory education for 5-6-year-olds. Despite being free of charge and legally mandated since early 2024, enrollment stood at just 38.4% (17,744 out of 46,217 children) in the 2023/2024 academic year. This underperformance reflects deeper systemic challenges such as inadequate enforcement mechanisms, regional disparities in service availability, and socio-economic barriers faced by families.

Table 1 provides a detailed overview of public and private ECEC enrollment in Kosovo, highlighting the depth of these shortfalls relative to European targets:

Table 1. Kosovo’s ECEC Enrollment vs. Barcelona Targets

Age Group	Population (2024)	Enrolled in ECEC	Enrollment Rate	Barcelona Target
Ages 0-2	~44,000	~4,356	~9.9%	45%
Ages 3-5 (excl. prep)	~66,000	~10,718	~16.2%	96%
Ages 5-6 (prep)	46,217	17,744	~38.4%	96%

Source: Kosovo Agency of Statistics (2024). Enrollment rates are author’s own calculations.

Despite the clear enrollment gaps and the underperformance in meeting the Barcelona targets, these aggregate figures only tell part of the story. Beyond the overall shortfall in institutional capacity and participation, deeper patterns of inequality emerge when examining *who actually*

gains access to the limited public ECEC spaces that do exist. Access is not only constrained by the number of available places but also by *how* those places are allocated.

Inequalities in Access to Public ECEC. A key source of inequality in Kosovo’s public Early Childhood Education and Care (ECEC) system lies in its admission criteria, which systematically favor children of dual-earner families. Municipal regulations across Kosovo commonly prioritize children whose both parents are formally employed, under the rationale that these households have the greatest logistical need for childcare during working hours (Behrami, Pacolli & Ramqaj, 2020). While seemingly efficient from a demand-management perspective, this logic produces exclusionary outcomes. It effectively marginalizes children from unemployed or informally employed households, particularly low-income families who are often deemed ineligible due to the lack of formal employment status, despite having an arguably greater developmental need for high-quality early education (Demas et al., 2021). These families are often left with no choice but to turn to private ECEC providers, where monthly fees can be more than double those of public services, placing a heavy financial burden on already disadvantaged households. Rather than mitigating inequality, current enrollment practices reproduce it by channeling limited public resources toward socioeconomically advantaged families who already enjoy higher levels of educational and economic capital. This reflects a classic “Matthew effect” in early childhood policy: those with more resources receive more support, while those with fewer resources are left behind (Merton, 1968).

Workforce Gaps and Gendered Norms in Kosovo’s ECEC. The quality and professional preparedness of Early Childhood Education and Care (ECEC) staff are central to broader public trust in the sector. In Kosovo, however, significant gaps persist in the qualification levels of educators, particularly between those working with younger versus older preschool-aged children, revealing structural neglect and underinvestment in the earliest years. According to data from the Education Management Information System (EMIS), as of 2018, the majority of educators working with children aged 0 to 3 possess only a secondary school diploma (206 out of 212), while just five hold a university-level degree (Gjelaj, Rraci & Bajrami, 2018). This mismatch between staff qualifications and the developmental needs of very young children is concerning, especially given the scientific consensus that the first three years of life are a foundational period for cognitive, emotional, and social development. For children aged 3 to 6, staff qualifications are

generally stronger. Most educators hold a university degree in education or have undergone formal requalification from the former two-year pedagogical training model to the current four-year bachelor system.

The ECEC workforce in Kosovo is almost entirely female, data from ASK shows that only four men were employed in 2023/2024 compared to 765 women, reflecting entrenched cultural norms that equate caregiving with women. This feminization not only mirrors broader patterns of occupational segregation in Kosovo but also reinforces gendered expectations for children, who rarely encounter male role models in early education.

The occupational segregation seen in the ECEC workforce parallels wider labor market patterns in Kosovo, where women remain disproportionately responsible for unpaid care and are underrepresented in formal employment. Thus, the gender composition of ECEC institutions not only reflects societal expectations about gender roles but also helps reproduce them. This context provides a critical foundation for understanding broader patterns of gender inequality in Kosovo particularly the persistent barriers to women's labor force participation. In the next section, I turn to these broader structural and normative constraints that shape how women navigate work, care, and employment in the Kosovar context.

4.4 Barriers to Women's Labor Market Participation in Kosovo

Despite notable educational gains among women in Kosovo, the country continues to record one of the lowest female labor force participation (FLFP) rates in Europe. In 2024, only 21.2% of women of working age were employed, compared to 55.9% of men, a gender gap of 34.7 percentage points (ASK, 2024). This disparity persists despite rising female secondary and tertiary completion rates, highlighting the mismatch between educational attainment and labor market integration.

Economic inactivity is both widespread and gendered. Nearly three-quarters of working-age women (74.1%) are economically inactive, compared to 39.4% of men (ASK, 2024). While men often cite education or job search as reasons for inactivity, women overwhelmingly report unpaid care, particularly childcare, as the main barrier (UN Women, 2024). This burden is not only unequal but massive: women perform on average 6.2 hours of unpaid care daily compared to men's 3.5, a contribution valued at €2.8 billion annually, or roughly 33% of Kosovo's GDP (Drevinja &

Ymeri, 2022). These figures underscore how unpaid labor constrains women's economic participation while simultaneously sustaining household and national economies.

Policy design further reinforces this imbalance. Kosovo's Labor Law (Law No. 03/L-212) grants women up to 12 months of maternity leave, though only partially paid, while fathers are entitled to just three days. This asymmetry entrenches caregiving as women's responsibility and limits men's involvement. Evidence from other contexts suggests that such lengthy, gendered leave schemes can lower women's likelihood of returning to the labor market, particularly where cultural norms already feminize care (Olivetti & Petrongolo, 2017).

Understanding these dynamics is complicated by gaps in official data: labor force surveys do not disaggregate participation by parental status or child age. This makes it impossible to assess how many women exit the labor market specifically due to childcare responsibilities, a critical blind spot in a context of scarce childcare services and entrenched gender roles.

Finally, normative expectations exacerbate these structural barriers. Patriarchal attitudes position women primarily as caregivers, rendering paid work secondary or even incompatible with their perceived family role (UN Women, 2024). Employers often share these assumptions: small firms in particular cite motherhood and caregiving duties as reasons to avoid hiring women (Drevinja & Ymeri, 2022). Such practices reinforce what scholars call the "motherhood penalty," where women are seen as less reliable employees. This creates a self-reinforcing cycle in which prevailing norms discourage women's employment, and low female employment rates in turn sustain traditional expectations.

5 Methodology

5.1 Research Design

This study employs a quantitative research design based on primary data collection through an online survey. The survey instrument was structured with two complementary components. The first component was a *cross-sectional questionnaire* designed to capture real-life patterns of maternal employment, childcare use, and perceived accessibility, alongside household dynamics and gender role attitudes. The second component was an embedded *factorial survey experiment (FSE)*, which systematically varied contextual conditions such as child's age, partner support, job flexibility, and childcare affordability, across hypothetical scenarios. By asking respondents to evaluate these scenarios, the FSE makes it possible to identify the causal influence of structural and household conditions on normative expectations about maternal employment. The rationale for combining these two approaches was to strengthen both the external and internal validity of the study.

Data were collected between July 4 and 30, 2025, via LimeSurvey, a secure online platform compliant with the EU's General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and hosted by the Computer-Assisted Web Interviewing (CAWI) Laboratory at the University of Tübingen. The final analytic sample includes 241 fully complete questionnaires, with an average completion time of 10-12 minutes.

All analyses in this thesis follow a complete-case approach: partially completed questionnaires were excluded from both descriptive and inferential analyses to ensure measurement comparability across modules and to avoid ad hoc assumptions about missing data. These partial responses have been archived and may be considered in future extensions of the study (e.g., exploratory descriptives or sensitivity analyses), but they do not contribute to the present results.

5.2 Sampling Strategy

Given the absence of a centralized database of parents with young children in Kosovo, this study employed a purposive, multi-channel recruitment strategy to target parents with at least one child under the age of six. The sampling approach was designed to maximize demographic and regional diversity within the constraints of non-probability sampling. While all regions of Kosovo were

represented, the distribution of respondents was not strictly proportional to the population (see Appendix B). Participants were recruited through three main pathways:

(1) *Municipality-Based Facebook Groups*. The survey link was manually disseminated across more than twelve active local community groups, widely used in Kosovo for information exchange and survey distribution. This ensured broad geographic coverage, including rural and non-capital areas.

(2) *NGO Partnerships and Institutional Networks*. Partnerships were established with four non-governmental organizations operating in the domains of education, gender equality, and maternal and child health. These partnerships enabled the study to reach its core target population through trusted intermediaries:

- The Kosovo Education Center (KEC) and Pedagogical Institute of Kosovo supported distribution by circulating the survey link through its internal mailing list and participants contact database.
- Kosovo Women for Women (KW4W) shared the survey with members of their women's empowerment and economic inclusion programs. This was achieved via email distribution lists used by KW4W to maintain contact with female beneficiaries across different regions. As such, this channel was particularly effective in reaching parents with diverse labor market experiences and socio-economic backgrounds.
- The NGO Action for Mothers and Children (AMC) coordinated with municipal health departments across Kosovo and disseminated the survey to local nurses working in maternal and child health units. These nurses, in turn, shared the survey with parents during routine health visits. This method proved essential in reaching mothers of very young children (ages 0-3).

(3) *Sponsored Social Media Campaign*. Third, a dedicated project Facebook page was used to run a targeted advertisement campaign. Facebook's algorithm optimized delivery to parents based on location, behaviors, and interests. The campaign reached several thousand users and generated 662 direct link clicks, extending participation beyond organized networks.

Despite efforts to maximize diversity, the sample has some limitations. Fathers are strongly underrepresented, but this does not compromise the analytical focus of the study. Since all core hypotheses in the cross-sectional component explicitly concern maternal employment as the dependent variable, the lack of male respondents does not affect hypothesis testing or the validity of findings regarding mothers. The main consequence is that the data cannot be used to conduct systematic gender comparisons between mothers and fathers in relation to employment, childcare use, and perceptions of accessibility. The results should therefore be interpreted as capturing maternal patterns rather than representative of all parents in Kosovo. Future research with more balanced gender samples would be valuable for examining paternal perspectives and dual-parent dynamics, but this lies beyond the scope of the present thesis.

The sample also likely skews toward more educated and digitally connected parents, even though urban-rural representation is comparatively balanced. Finally, the survey did not include a question on how respondents accessed the link (e.g., via Facebook, NGOs, or the advertisement), which limits transparency about recruitment channel effectiveness. These constraints are inherent to non-probability sampling and are taken into account when interpreting the results. Given its non-probability nature, the sample is not statistically representative of all parents in Kosovo.

5.3 Variable Operationalization

This study operationalizes its central constructs through a structured set of survey questions, which were taken from established international instruments to ensure validity and comparability. Variables are presented below according to their role in the analytical framework: dependent, independent, mediating and moderating variables.

Childcare Accessibility (Independent Variable). Childcare accessibility serves as the principal independent variable in this study. It was measured in two complementary ways: (1) reported usage data providing descriptive evidence of actual childcare arrangements, and (2) perceived accessibility items forming the explanatory basis for hypothesis testing.

(1) *Reported usage data* were measured with items adapted from the European Quality of Life Survey (EQLS, 2016). Respondents indicated the main type of childcare used for their youngest child (Q11), the number of hours per week in formal care (Q12), and monthly childcare costs (Q12a). Parents whose children attended formal care also rated their satisfaction with six service

characteristics, including facilities, group size, staff professionalism, personal attention, parent–staff communication, and curriculum (Q13a–Q13f). These measures provide descriptive evidence of actual childcare arrangements in Kosovo.

(2) *Perceived accessibility* was assessed using items from the Early Years of Parents Study (2023). Respondents rated the affordability of local childcare (Q14), the ease of finding a provider able to meet their child’s needs (Q15), the sufficiency of available childcare places (Q16), and the overall quality of services in their area (Q17). Responses were captured on five-point categorical scales. These items reflect subjective evaluations of structural access conditions and form the explanatory basis for hypothesis testing.

Maternal Employment (Dependent Variable). Maternal employment is the principal dependent variable in the cross-sectional analysis. Following the *European Quality of Life Survey (EQLS, 2016)*, employment status was measured by distinguishing full-time, part-time, self-employment, maternity leave, unemployment, homemaking, student, and other categories (Q8). For employed respondents, weekly working hours were reported (Q8b). For non-employed respondents, reasons for not participating in paid work were collected (Q8a). For analysis, employment was recoded into a binary outcome distinguishing *working* (employed full-time, part-time, self-employed, or on maternity leave) versus *non-working* (unemployed, homemaker, student, or other).

Social Norms (Mediating Variable). Social norms were measured with items adapted from the Gender Norms Scale (G-NORM; Sedlander et al., 2022), complemented by a short scale of gender-essentialist beliefs. *Descriptive norms* (what people typically do) were assessed with three items (Q18a–Q18c; 5-point Likert) about task specialization and maternal employment (e.g., whether mothers of young children usually stay at home). A composite *Descriptive Norms Index* was constructed as the mean of these items. The reliability coefficient ($\alpha = 0.67$) falls just below the conventional threshold of 0.70 but is acceptable given the small number of items and conceptual coherence. *Prescriptive norms* (what people believe should happen) were measured with parallel statements (Q19a–Q19c; 5-point Likert) on perceived community expectations (e.g., that childcare should be a woman’s responsibility or that men should be the sole earners). A composite *Prescriptive Norms Index* was constructed as the mean of these items. This scale showed high internal consistency (Cronbach’s $\alpha = 0.82$). In addition, *Gender essentialism* was measured with three items adapted from Gaunt (2006) (Q25a–Q25c; 5-point Likert), capturing endorsement of the

view that mothers are naturally better suited to childcare than fathers. Responses were averaged into a *Gender Essentialism Index*. Reliability analysis indicated acceptable internal consistency (Cronbach's $\alpha = 0.695$).

Relative Income (Moderating Variable). Relative income, conceptualized as a moderating factor, was measured using two complementary indicators that capture both objective and subjective dimensions. The *objective* measure asked respondents to estimate the percentage of total household income they personally contributed (Q9b; open numeric field). The *subjective* measure, adapted from the International Social Survey Programme (ISSP, 2012), asked respondents to compare their earnings with their partner's on a categorical scale ranging from "my income is much higher" to "my partner's income is much higher" (Q10). Taken together, these indicators provide a multidimensional account of women's financial bargaining position within households.

Partner Support (Moderating Variable). Partner support was operationalized in both instrumental and emotional dimensions, drawing on items from the *Generations and Gender Survey II (2022)*. Instrumental support was captured through task-specific questions on household labor (Q20a-Q20f) (e.g., laundry, cooking, shopping, repairs) and childcare responsibilities (Q21a-Q21e) (e.g., dressing children, caring for them when ill, bedtime routines, helping with homework). Respondents indicated who usually performed these tasks using a scale that ranged from "always me" to "always my partner," with an additional option for "someone else". Two composite indices were created: the *Housework Division Index* (mean of six items) and the *Childcare Division Index* (mean of five items). Reliability analysis indicated acceptable internal consistency for the housework index (Cronbach's $\alpha = 0.669$) and high consistency for the childcare index ($\alpha = 0.883$). Higher values on both indices indicate a more equal division of tasks. Emotional support was measured with two single-item indicators (Q24a-Q24b; 5-point Likert): *Partner encourages career* and *Partner supports formal care*. The former assesses the extent to which the partner encourages the respondent to pursue her career goals, while the latter measures support for her decisions regarding the use of formal childcare services.

Survey Adaptation and Validation. All survey items were first translated into Albanian by the author and then reviewed by native speakers with expertise in social research to ensure linguistic accuracy and contextual relevance. To further validate clarity and comprehension, the questionnaire was pilot-tested with three respondents in person prior to data collection.

5.4 Factorial Survey Experiment: Design and Implementation

The factorial survey experiment (FSE) was implemented as the final module of the questionnaire. It introduced respondents to short, hypothetical scenarios (vignettes) about a fictional mother, Arta, with experimentally varied contextual conditions. This section details the vignette design, randomization procedure, sample size, and measurement of dependent variables.

Table 2. *Dimensions and Levels of Vignettes in the Factorial Survey Experiment*

Dimension	Levels
Child's age	(1) 1 year old (2) 5 years old
Partner support	(1) Fully supportive (2) Rarely helps (3) Prefers she stays home
Work flexibility	(1) Remote work (2) Fixed hours (9-17) (3) Shift work
Childcare affordability	(1) Low income + subsidy (€350, €70 subsidy, €80 fee) (2) Medium income, no subsidy (€550, €150 fee) (3) Higher income, no subsidy (€750, €150 fee)

A full factorial design was implemented, resulting in 54 unique vignette combinations ($2 \times 3 \times 3 \times 3$). These combinations were generated using an R script that systematically combined each level of the four experimental dimensions. Each respondent was presented with three vignettes, randomly selected from the full set of 54, and asked to evaluate *Arta's* situation in each one. The number of vignettes per respondent was limited to three to reduce cognitive fatigue and ensure careful consideration of each scenario, in line with established best practices in factorial survey design (Auspurg & Hinz, 2015).

Randomization Procedure. Given LimeSurvey's limited functionality for advanced experimental randomization, a custom randomization workaround was developed. First, all 54 unique vignettes were randomized in Excel and manually grouped into sets of three, resulting in a series of predefined vignette groups. These groups were then assigned unique identifiers and imported into LimeSurvey. A hidden equation-type question was used to randomly assign one of these vignette groups to each respondent. Randomization quality was checked by comparing vignette distribution across respondents; no significant imbalances were detected.

Sample size and vignette evaluations. The factorial module was completed by 241 respondents, resulting in a total of 723 vignette-level observations ($241 \times 3 = 723$). Given the 54 unique vignette combinations in the design, each vignette was evaluated on average 13 to 14 times, assuming uniform randomization across all groups.

Operationalization of Vignette Outcomes. Each vignette was followed by three evaluative questions designed to measure injunctive normative expectations about maternal employment and childcare. These questions operationalize how respondents believe a mother *should* behave in the described situation, thereby capturing normative judgments rather than personal preferences.

Support for maternal employment (Q26) was measured by asking whether Arta should return to work full-time, on a 5-point ordinal scale ranging from *Definitely not* to *Definitely yes*. This variable captures general approval or disapproval of maternal employment given the contextual conditions described in the vignette.

Preferred maternal working hours (Q27) was measured by asking respondents to indicate the number of hours Arta should work if she returns to employment. Response options were categorical, ranging from *0 hours (stay at home)* to *40 or more hours per week*. This measure provides a more fine-grained evaluation of the perceived appropriateness of different levels of maternal employment intensity.

Preferred childcare hours (Q28) was measured by asking how much time Arta's child should spend in formal childcare each day, with four ordered categories: *None, cared for at home*; *A few hours on selected days*; *Half day, every day*; and *Full day, every day*. This item captures normative expectations regarding children's appropriate exposure to non-parental care.

Together, these three dependent variables provide complementary insights into how respondents evaluate maternal employment and childcare use under varying contextual conditions. For the complete vignette texts, full dimension descriptions, and exact survey wording of all follow-up questions, see Appendix A, Part 2.

5.5 Ethical Considerations

This study was conducted in accordance with the usage agreement with the CAWI-Labor of the Institute of Sociology at the University of Tübingen, which governs access to LimeSurvey and sets

out obligations regarding participant rights and data protection. Participation was voluntary, and at the start of the questionnaire respondents received an informed consent statement outlining the study's purpose, duration, data handling, and their right to withdraw at any time. No personal identifiers (e.g., names, email addresses, IP addresses) were collected, and all responses were stored anonymously. Respondents could skip any question, and no incentives were offered. The survey did not target vulnerable populations or ask for sensitive personal data. The factorial survey experiment presented everyday work–family scenarios phrased in a neutral, nonjudgmental manner to avoid distress or bias. All data were securely downloaded after fieldwork and are used exclusively for academic purposes.

5.6 Data Preparation

The dataset exported from LimeSurvey contained responses to both the cross-sectional questionnaire and the factorial survey experiment in a single wide-format file. To align with the dual design of the study, the data were split into two analytic files: a cross-sectional dataset (one row per respondent) and a factorial survey dataset (multiple vignette evaluations per respondent).

Cross-sectional dataset. The raw LimeSurvey export included all started surveys, but only fully submitted questionnaires (i.e., cases with a recorded submission timestamp) were retained for analysis. Questionnaire variables were renamed from technical survey IDs (e.g., g01q02) to descriptive labels (e.g., gender; care_hours_wk) and harmonized with value labels from the questionnaire. Derived variables were created to capture key constructs, such as employment status (is_working, is_nonworking) and use of formal childcare (formalcare). Structural routing was enforced: employment-related items were set to missing for non-working respondents, childcare-related items for non-users, and partner-related items for those without a partner. This ensured internal consistency across the dataset.

Factorial survey dataset. Vignette responses were originally stored in wide format, with three vignette evaluations per respondent across multiple sets. The dataset was reshaped into long format using Stata's reshape long procedure, producing one row per vignette evaluation. Each vignette was then merged with its experimentally varied attributes (child's age, partner support, work flexibility, childcare affordability) imported from the vignette design file. This resulted in a vignette-level dataset (N = 723), which retained respondent identifiers for clustering of standard errors and linkage to covariates from the cross-sectional module.

Missing values. Missingness was systematically reviewed using descriptive checks and Stata's `misstable summarize`. Household income required additional preparation: cases reporting only an income band were assigned the midpoint of the chosen range, while cases reporting "0" income without a band were set to missing. No multiple imputation was applied, as missingness largely reflected structural routing rather than item nonresponse.

Outlier treatment. To ensure the validity of the analyses, all continuous variables were screened for implausible or extreme values. Observations outside substantively plausible ranges were recoded to missing rather than retained or imputed. Reported weekly working hours were excluded if equal to zero or greater than 80, as such values are inconsistent with realistic employment patterns. For respondents using formal childcare, weekly childcare hours were restricted to a 0-70 range and monthly childcare costs to €0-600, reflecting typical institutional opening times and local market conditions. Household net income values were top-coded at €4,000 per month to reduce the influence of extreme right-tail cases, while any reported amount above €10,000 was set to missing. Finally, respondents' reported share of household income was constrained to the 0-100% interval, with values outside this range set to missing. These procedures strike a balance between eliminating clearly invalid data and retaining genuine variability in the distributions, thereby safeguarding both the robustness and interpretability of the results.

5.7 Analytical Strategy

The analysis combines descriptive statistics with multivariate regression models. Descriptive statistics are first used to profile the sample and provide an overview of childcare use, satisfaction, and accessibility. For the cross-sectional component, logistic regression models estimate the association between perceived childcare accessibility and maternal employment, controlling for socio-demographic and economic covariates. Mediation analyses are conducted using KHB decomposition to assess whether social norms account for part of this relationship, while moderation analyses test interactions with partner support and relative income. For the factorial survey experiment, multilevel linear regression models with random intercepts at the respondent level analyze how experimentally varied conditions (child's age, partner support, job flexibility, childcare affordability) shape normative expectations about maternal employment, working hours, and childcare use.

6 Descriptive Statistics

6.1 Sample Characteristics

Table 3 presents an overview of the sample characteristics. A total of 241 valid respondents participated in the survey. The majority of respondents were female (89.6%), while male respondents accounted for 10.4% of the sample.

The average age of respondents was 32.6 years (SD = 5.77), with a minimum of 21 and a maximum of 54 years, suggesting a relatively young parenting population. Among those who reported having at least one child under the age of 18, the average number of children was 1.90 (SD = 0.94), with a median of 2. The number of children ranged from 1 to 6, indicating that while many respondents had one or two children, a smaller portion had larger families.

In terms of residential location, 69.3% lived in urban areas (cities or towns), and 30.7% in rural settings (villages or the countryside). Educational attainment was relatively high: 43.2% held a bachelor's degree and 29.9% a master's degree, while only a small proportion have completed only lower secondary school (2.9%).

Table 3. Summary of Key Sample Characteristics

	Mean	SD	Min	Max	Median	N
Age	32.61	5.775	21	54	32	241
My share of HH income (%)	33.03	30.696	0	100	32.50	202
HH net income (EUR) [exact or band midpoint]	1,213.19	971.20	100	4000	900	241
# children <18	1.901	0.94	1	6	2	172
Hours/week (job)	33.702	14.82	2	60	40	136
	Summary					
N (%)						241
Female					(89.6%)	216
Male					(10.4%)	25
<i>Urban/Rural</i>						
Urban (city or town)					(69.3%)	167
Rural (village or countryside)					(30.7%)	74
<i>Education</i>						
Lower secondary school (class 6-9)					(2.9%)	7
Upper secondary school (class 10-12)					(21.2%)	51
Bachelor's degree					(43.2%)	104
Master's degree					(29.9%)	72
Doctoral degree (PhD)					(2.9%)	7

The mean reported monthly household net income was €1,213 with a standard deviation of €971 indicating considerable variation in household economic conditions. The median income was €900, confirming a right-skewed distribution where a minority of higher-income households elevate the average.

Figure 4.1 displays the distribution of monthly household net income, based on either exact values or midpoint estimates derived from income bands. Most respondents reported incomes between €250 and €1,500, with the modal group centered around €750 (reported by 27% of the sample). Beyond €2,000, the number of households in each income bracket declines markedly, with only a few reporting incomes approaching the cap of €4,000. The histogram confirms the positive skew of the income distribution. Despite the cap, the relatively high standard deviation reflects ongoing heterogeneity across the sample.

Figure 2. *Distribution of Monthly Household Net Income (EUR)*

6.2 Employment Patterns

Table 4 presents the distribution of employment status across respondents. As shown in Table 4, full-time employment was the most common status overall (42.3%). A larger share of male respondents (76%) than female respondents (38.4%) reported full-time work¹. Among women, substantial proportions reported being unemployed for over a year (21.3%) or working as full-time

¹ The male subsample is very small (N = 25), so results should be interpreted with caution.

caregivers or homemakers (18.1%). In contrast, no men in the sample reported either of these statuses. Maternity leave also accounted for a notable share among women (8.3%). Although part-time and self-employment were reported by small minorities across genders, these categories were more common among women than men.

Table 4. Employment Status by Gender

	Gender		Total
	Female	Male	
N	216 (89.6%)	25 (10.4%)	241 (100.0%)
Employment status			
Employed full-time	(38.4%) 83	(76.0%) 19	(42.3%) 102
Employed part-time	(4.6%) 10	(4.0%) 1	(4.6%) 11
Self-employed	(3.7%) 8	(12.0%) 3	(4.6%) 11
Employed but currently on maternity leave	(8.3%) 18	(0.0%) 0	(7.5%) 18
Unemployed (less than 12 months)	(5.1%) 11	(8.0%) 2	(5.4%) 13
Unemployed (12 months or more)	(21.3%) 46	(0.0%) 0	(19.1%) 46
Homemaker / Full-time caregiver	(18.1%) 39	(0.0%) 0	(16.2%) 39
Student/in education	(0.5%) 1	(0.0%) 0	(0.4%) 1

Note: Interpret male column cautiously due to small N (N=25).

Due to the very small number of men who reported being outside the labor market (only two cases), the analysis of reasons for non-employment focuses primarily on women. Figure 3 illustrates the distribution of self-reported reasons among female respondents who were not working at the time of the survey. The majority of women cited home and care duties (49.5%) as their main reason for not participating in paid work. The second most common reason was inability to find a job (41.8%), pointing to structural constraints in the labor market that intersect with family responsibilities. Smaller shares of women reported being out of the labor force by choice (5.5%) or due to schooling and training (3.3%), while illness or disability was not reported as a reason in this sample.

Figure 3. Distribution of Self-Reported Reasons for Non-Employment Among Women

6.3 Childcare Usage and Costs (Objective Indicators)

Type of Childcare Used by Employment Status. Table 5 presents the distribution of childcare arrangements among surveyed households, disaggregated by maternal employment status. Overall, 23.7% of respondents used public Early Childhood Education and Care (ECEC) services, while 29.0% relied on private ECEC. Informal care arrangements, defined as care provided by parents at home, grandparents, other relatives, friends, or neighbors were reported by nearly half of the sample (49.8%).

Clear differences emerge between working and non-working mothers. Among employed respondents, 31.0% reported using public ECEC and 43.7% used private ECEC, compared with only 13.1% and 8.1%, respectively, among non-working mothers. Conversely, reliance on informal care was markedly higher among non-working mothers (80.8%) than among those in employment (28.2%). Supplementary tabulations of informal care subtypes indicate that this divergence is driven predominantly by “mother at home” arrangements. Nearly three-quarters (74.8%) of non-working mothers reported caring for their child themselves, compared with only 25.2% of working mothers. Other informal care forms, such as care by fathers (10 cases in total), grandparents (20 cases), or other relatives/friends (2 cases), were relatively uncommon and had little impact on the overall share of informal arrangements.

Table 5. *Type of Childcare Used by Employment Status*

	Not working	Working	Total
N	99 (41.1%)	142 (58.9%)	241 (100.0%)
Uses public ECEC	0.131 99	0.310 142	0.237 241
Uses private ECEC	0.081 99	0.437 142	0.290 241
Uses informal care	0.808 99	0.282 142	0.498 241

Values are proportions (mean of binary indicators). Employment: 1 = Working, 0 = Not working.

Satisfaction and Costs by Childcare Type. Table 6 and Figure 4 compare parental satisfaction and costs between public and private formal childcare. Across all satisfaction indicators, covering facilities, child-staff ratio, staff quality, attention to the child, parent communication, and curriculum, average ratings were high (around 4 out of 5) for both types, with no meaningful differences. This indicates that parents using either public or private formal care tend to report similarly positive experiences.

Differences emerged, however, in weekly usage and monthly costs. Children in private care attended an average of 26.2 hours per week, compared with 16.7 hours for public care. The cost

gap was substantial: median monthly fees were €132.50 in private care versus €40.00 in public care. Figure 4 shows that private care costs were more variable, with some families paying above €400 and an extreme case reaching €600. Public care costs were generally low, with a median of €40, though variation existed because fees are income-based: households with higher earnings paid somewhat more, while those with lower or median incomes paid less.

Table 6. Satisfaction and Costs by Childcare Type

	Public ECEC				Private ECEC			
	Mean	SD	Median	N	Mean	SD	Median	N
N	53 (43.1%)				70 (56.9%)			
Sat: facilities	4.09	0.98	4	53	4.11	0.84	4	70
Sat: child:staff ratio	3.84	1.40	4	51	4.16	1.09	5	66
Sat: staff quality	4.13	1.00	4	51	4.27	0.72	4	69
Sat: attention to child	3.88	1.01	4	51	3.92	1.11	4	69
Sat: parent communication	4.13	1.05	4	51	4.05	1.14	4	70
Sat: curriculum	4.29	0.87	5	51	4.10	0.99	4	70

Table 7. Hours/week and Costs by Childcare Type

	Public ECEC	Private ECEC
N	53 (43.1%)	70 (56.9%)
Childcare hours/week	16.71 (14.20) [8]	26.24 (14.96) [30]
Monthly childcare cost (EUR)	44.79 (41.33) [40]	148.54 (79.86) [132.50]

Note: Among users of formal childcare only.

Figure 4: Monthly Childcare Costs by Type

While objective indicators of childcare use and satisfaction, such as service type, weekly hours, and cost, are not directly used in hypothesis testing, they are presented first to contextualize broader patterns of childcare arrangements. The core analytical focus, however, lies in perceived childcare accessibility, measured through four indicators: affordability, ease of finding, availability of places, and overall quality. These items were answered by all respondents, ensuring a dataset that reflects both users' and non-users' perspectives.

6.4 Perceived Accessibility of Childcare Services

Each item was rated on a 5-point Likert scale, where 1 indicates a more favorable perception (e.g., *very affordable, very easy to find, very good quality*) and 5 indicates a more negative perception (e.g., *very expensive, very difficult to find, very poor quality*). Therefore, lower values represent more positive experiences, while higher values suggest perceived barriers or dissatisfaction.

Affordability. Respondents evaluated the affordability of local childcare services with a mean score of 3.36 (SD = 1.28), suggesting moderate to low affordability. The median response was 4, indicating that many respondents found childcare to be somewhat expensive, if not outright unaffordable. While a minority rated childcare as affordable (values 1-2), the overall distribution reflects a widespread perception of cost as a barrier.

Ease of Finding Local Childcare. Respondents rated the ease of finding a childcare provider near their home with a mean score of 3.34 (SD = 1.23) and a median of 4, indicating that most perceive this process as somewhat difficult. Very few selected the most positive options (“very easy” or “easy”), suggesting that finding accessible childcare close to home remains a logistical challenge for many families.

Availability of Places. The item on whether enough childcare places are available yielded a mean score of 3.72 (SD = 1.13) the least positive rating among all four indicators. The median was again 4, meaning that most respondents believe there are fewer places available than needed. A small number selected the most negative category (“much fewer places than needed”).

Perceived Quality. Respondents’ ratings of the overall quality of local childcare services were more favorable. The mean score was 2.66 (SD = 0.94), with a median of 3, indicating that quality is perceived as average to slightly good.

Table 8. *Perceived Accessibility of Childcare Services*

	Summary				
N					241
Perceived affordability	3.363	(1.280)	1.000	5.000	4.000 237
Perceived ease of finding local childcare	3.337	(1.234)	1.000	5.000	4.000 240
Perceived availability of places	3.718	(1.134)	1.000	5.000	4.000 234
Perceived quality	2.661	(0.938)	1.000	5.000	3.000 239

Notes: Measured on a 1-5 Likert scale; lower values = more positive perception.

6.5 Social Norms: Descriptive and Prescriptive Expectations Around Gender Roles

Table 9 and Figure 5 present summary statistics for the indices capturing descriptive norms (beliefs about what most people do) and prescriptive norms (beliefs about what most people should do). As shown in Table 9, the index has a mean of 2.37 (SD = 0.90), with a median of 2.33, indicating a moderately egalitarian perception of societal norms. The interquartile range (1.67-3.00) suggests some variation, but most respondents leaned toward rejecting rigid traditional expectations.

The prescriptive norms index yielded a lower mean of 2.04 (SD = 0.96) and a median of 2.00, suggesting a stronger lean toward egalitarian ideals. However, as the right-skewed distribution in Figure 5 illustrates, a minority of respondents strongly endorsed traditional gender prescriptions, contributing to a skewness value of 1.10.

Table 9. Summary Statistics for Descriptive and Prescriptive Social Norms Indices

Indicator	Mean	SD	Min	Max	25th pctl	Median	75th pctl	IQR	Skewness
Descriptive norms	2.37	0.89	1.00	5.00	1.66	2.33	3.00	1.33	0.46
Prescriptive norms	2.04	0.96	1.00	5.00	1.33	2.00	2.33	1.00	1.10

Figure 5. Distribution Comparison of Descriptive vs. Prescriptive Social Norms Indices

6.6 Partner Support as a Moderating Variable

As shown in Table 10, the mean values for instrumental support were moderate, at 2.592 (SD = 0.768) for housework and 2.251 (SD = 0.873) for childcare, suggesting a less-than-equal division of unpaid labor. Emotional support scores were higher, averaging 3.926 (SD = 1.205) for career encouragement and 4.148 (SD = 1.112) for support of formal childcare, indicating that partners tended to express more support in principle than was reflected in the actual division of domestic and childcare responsibilities.

Table 10. Composite Indices: Partner Instrumental and Emotional Support

	Summary			
N				241
Housework division index ¹	2.592 (0.768)	1.000	5.000	2.667 240
Childcare division index ¹	2.251 (0.873)	1.000	5.000	2.200 240
Partner encourages career ²	3.926 (1.205)	1.000	5.000	4.000 231
Partner supports formal care ²	4.148 (1.112)	1.000	5.000	5.000 230

¹ Index scores computed as the mean of standardized items; higher values indicate a more equal division of housework/childcare between partners.

² Items measured on a 5-point Likert scale (1 = strongly disagree, 5 = strongly agree); higher values indicate stronger partner support.

To better contextualize these scores, task-level data on housework and childcare were examined separately by gender. These analyses reveal a consistent gender imbalance: female respondents overwhelmingly reported being solely or mostly responsible for domestic and caregiving tasks, especially for routine care work such as laundry, cleaning, and staying home when children are ill. In contrast, male respondents, though only a small subsample (N=25) showed a clear and unanimous pattern of reporting that their partner is mainly responsible for such tasks. This reinforces the interpretation that emotional support may not translate into practical involvement in unpaid labor. For detailed breakdowns by task and gender, see Tables in Appendix C.

6.7 Relative Income (Objective and Subjective Measures)

Objective Measure: Mother's Share of Household Income. As shown in Figure 6, the distribution of mothers' share of household income is highly skewed. Among the 202 valid responses, the average contribution was 33.03% (SD = 30.70), with considerable variation. The median share was 32.5%, while the interquartile range spans from 0% (P25) to 50% (P75), indicating that at least one-quarter of mothers reported no personal income, while another quarter contributed half or more to the household income. A substantial proportion of respondents cluster at the lower end, particularly at 0%, underscoring the persistence of single-earner arrangements where only the partner contributes economically. Notably, a modest concentration of responses appears around

the 50% mark, suggesting a subset of households where income is equally split. Yet, the broader spread in the distribution highlights the heterogeneity in household economic arrangements among mothers, ranging from full dependency to majority earners.

Figure 6. *Distribution of Mother's Share of Household Income*

Subjective Measure: “Who Earns More?”. The subjective perception of relative earnings provides complementary insight into intra-household economic roles (Figure 7). Among the 241 respondents, the majority (47.3%) reported that their partner earns more, followed by 15.8% who stated that they have no personal income, and 14.9% indicating earnings are about the same. Only 13.7% of mothers perceived themselves as earning more than their partner, and a small minority indicated either having a partner without income (5.4%) or no partner (2.5%). Given that the sample is predominantly mothers, these distributions likely reflect households where partners report higher earnings; detailed implications are examined in Section 7.1 (H4).

Figure 7. *Subjective Perceptions of Relative Earnings Within the Household*

7 Results

7.1 Cross-Sectional Survey Results

We now test **Hypothesis 1** using logistic regressions: Model 1 includes perceived childcare accessibility only; Model 2 adds socio-demographic and economic controls.

Model 1, presented in Table 11, includes only the four perceived accessibility measures as predictors. The findings indicate a strong and statistically significant negative association between perceived affordability and maternal employment ($b = -0.601, p < 0.01$). The negative coefficient implies that mothers who view childcare as more unaffordable have a substantially lower likelihood of being employed, even when the other accessibility dimensions are held constant. This coefficient corresponds to an odds ratio of 0.55, meaning that each one-unit increase in perceived unaffordability reduces the odds of maternal employment by about 45%. Model 1 explains approximately 10.6% of the variation in maternal employment (Pseudo $R^2 = 0.106$) and is statistically significant overall ($\chi^2 = 30.29, p < 0.001$).

Table 11. Logistic regression (Model 1): Childcare Accessibility and Maternal Employment

	(1)
Mother employed (1 = yes, 0 = no)	
Perceived affordability	-0.601*** (0.130)
Enough places available	0.132 (0.142)
Perceived quality	-0.135 (0.172)
Ease of finding nearby childcare	-0.015 (0.140)
Constant	2.209*** (0.765)
N	209
Log likelihood	-128.226
Chi-squared	30.286
Prob > chi2	0.000
Pseudo R ²	0.106

Standard errors in parentheses. Coefficients are log-odds (not odds ratios).

Higher values indicate: less affordability, fewer places, lower quality, and more difficulty finding nearby care.

Sample: mothers (gender = 1); all respondents have ≥ 1 child under age 6.

Estimation: logistic regression.

* $p < 0.10$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$

Model 2 (Table 12) adds socio-demographic and economic controls. The affordability effect remains negative and statistically significant ($b = -0.585, p < 0.01$), with a magnitude similar to

Model 1, confirming the robustness of this association even after adjusting for controls. The non-significance of availability and quality is unchanged. Among controls, rural residence is associated with lower employment ($b = -0.809$, $SE = 0.410$, $p < .05$), and household income is positively related to employment ($b = 0.001$, $SE \approx 0.000$, $p < .01$). Age is not significant. Relative to *Upper secondary school* (10-12), Master's attainment is positively associated with employment ($b = 1.231$, $SE = 0.531$, $p < .05$), whereas Bachelor's is not. The increase in explanatory power (Pseudo R^2 from 0.106 to 0.253) shows that both childcare affordability and household resources jointly shape maternal employment.

Table 12. Logistic regression (Model 2): Childcare Accessibility and Maternal Employment (with Controls)

	(1)
Mother employed (1 = yes, 0 = no)	
Perceived affordability	-0.585***
	(0.146)
Enough places available	0.111
	(0.160)
Perceived quality	-0.201
	(0.195)
Age	0.034
	(0.033)
Lower secondary school (class 6-9)	-1.817
	(1.531)
Bachelor's degree	0.433
	(0.480)
Master's degree	1.231**
	(0.531)
Rural (village or countryside)	-0.809**
	(0.410)
Household income (€)	0.001***
	(0.000)
Constant	-0.077
	(1.354)
N	203
Log likelihood	-104.453
Chi-squared	70.732
Prob > chi2	0.000
Pseudo R ²	0.253

Standard errors in parentheses. Coefficients are log-odds (not odds ratios). Higher values indicate: less affordability, fewer places, and lower quality. Sample: mothers (gender = 1); all respondents have ≥ 1 child under age 6.
 * $p < 0.10$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$

Taken together, the results provide partial but important support for Hypothesis 1: among the three accessibility dimensions, only affordability shows a robust association with maternal employment in Kosovo. This suggests that accessibility is primarily experienced through cost barriers rather than availability or quality. While the conceptual framework treated accessibility as multidimensional, the evidence highlights affordability as the decisive factor, motivating the focus of Hypotheses 2-4 on mechanisms operating specifically through affordability.

I now turn to **Hypothesis 2**, which examines whether the affordability–employment link is mediated by social norms. This is tested with logistic regression-based KHB decomposition models, which allow assessment of mediation while accounting for the nonlinear nature of logistic models and adjusting for sociodemographic controls (age, education, urban/rural residence, number of children under 18, and household income).

Three nested models are presented. Model A introduces descriptive norms as a potential mediator, testing whether mothers who perceive childcare as unaffordable are also embedded in environments where few mothers work, which could reinforce withdrawal from the labor market. Model B focuses on prescriptive norms, exploring whether internalized beliefs about what mothers ought to do mediate the affordability-employment link. In Model C, we extend this by including gender essentialist beliefs, which may operate alongside prescriptive norms to shape mothers’ choices, even when structural barriers like affordability are accounted for.

Table 13. *KHB Decomposition of the Effect of Childcare Affordability on Maternal Employment*

Predictor	Model A: Descriptive Norms	Model B: Prescriptive Norms	Model C: Prescriptive Norms + Gender Essentialism
Perceived affordability			
Reduced model coefficient	-0.648*	-0.642*	-0.644*
Full model coefficient	-0.641*	-0.641*	-0.634*
Indirect effect (Diff)	-0.0065	-0.0004	-0.0092
p-value for mediation	0.910	0.941	0.707
Confounding %	1.01%	0.06%	1.43%
Model fit (Pseudo R ²)	0.28	0.27	0.27

Notes: Models include controls for age, education, urban/rural, and household income.

Coefficients are log-odds.

Higher values of 'perc_ afford' indicate less affordable childcare.

***p < 0.01.

Across Models A-C (Table 13), affordability remains large, negative, and statistically significant in both reduced and full specifications, confirming its robust direct effect on maternal employment.

By contrast, the indirect effects through descriptive norms (Diff = -0.0065, $p = .91$), prescriptive norms (Diff = -0.0004, $p = .94$), and gender essentialism (Diff = -0.0092, $p = .71$) are uniformly negligible, with confounding percentages below 1.5%. Taken together, these findings offer no support for Hypothesis 2: affordability operates as a structural constraint rather than one filtered through normative frameworks, suggesting that reducing the cost of childcare may be more effective in increasing maternal employment than norm-targeted campaigns alone.

Having established in Hypotheses 1 and 2 that perceived affordability is the pivotal accessibility dimension for maternal employment, **Hypothesis 3** examines whether this relationship varies by partner support. We distinguish emotional support (partner encourages the mother’s career; partner supports the use of formal childcare) and instrumental support (division of childcare and housework). We estimate four logistic models interacting perceived affordability with each moderator, adjusting for maternal age, education, and household income. Coefficients for controls are omitted for brevity (see table notes).

Emotional Support. Table 14 reports the two models with emotional support moderators. Neither interaction term is statistically significant (Encourages career \times affordability: $b = 0.033$, $SE = 0.110$; Supports formal care \times affordability: $b = 0.010$, $SE = 0.127$). Figure 8a and 8b illustrates predicted probabilities of maternal employment across affordability levels and support profiles. In both panels, employment probabilities decline as childcare is perceived as less affordable, while higher support is consistently associated with higher baseline employment. The lines are largely parallel, indicating level shifts rather than slope differences.

Table 14. Logit Model: Emotional Support \times Childcare Affordability and Maternal Employment

	(1)	(2)
	Mother is Employed	Mother is Employed
Mother is Employed		
Perceived Affordability	-0.701 (0.431)	-0.613 (0.539)
Partner Encourages Career	-0.104 (0.421)	
Perceived Affordability # Partner Encourages Career	0.0329 (0.110)	
Partner Supports Formal Care		0.191 (0.459)
Perceived Affordability # Partner Supports Formal Care		0.0104

		(0.127)
Constant	-1.704	-3.129
	(2.455)	(2.701)
Observations	204	205

Note: Controls included: age, education, urban/rural, and household income.

Standard errors in parentheses

* $p < 0.1$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$

Figure 8. Predicted Maternal Employment by Childcare Affordability, Moderated by Partner Support: (a) Career Encouragement; (b) Formal Childcare Support

Instrumental Support. Table 15 examines instrumental support. Again, the interaction terms are small and non-significant (Childcare division \times affordability: $b = -0.153$, $SE = 0.201$; Housework division \times affordability: $b = 0.059$, $SE = 0.197$). Figure 9a shows that when childcare is Affordable or Moderate, mothers in households with more equal childcare sharing display higher probabilities of employment compared to those with mixed or unequal divisions. However, at the Unaffordable end, the three lines converge to similarly low probabilities, suggesting affordability overrides the benefits of equal sharing. Figure 9b shows a similar gradient for housework division, with higher baseline employment when tasks are shared more equally, but again without evidence of slope differences.

Table 15. Logit Model: Affordability \times Instrumental Support and Maternal Employment

	(1)	(2)
	Mother is Employed	Mother is Employed
Mother is Employed		
Perceived Affordability	-0.294	-0.733
	(0.420)	(0.500)
Childcare Division	0.876	
	(0.769)	
Perceived Affordability # Childcare Division	-0.153	

	(0.201)	
Housework Division		0.0884
		(0.770)
Perceived Affordability # Housework Division		0.0585
		(0.197)
Constant	-4.330*	-2.454
	(2.551)	(2.701)
Observations	212	212

Note: Controls included: age, education, urban/rural, and household income.

Standard errors in parentheses

* $p < 0.1$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$

Figure 9. Predicted Maternal Employment by Childcare Affordability, Moderated by Instrumental Support (a) Childcare Division; (b) Housework Division

Thus, we find no statistical support for Hypothesis 3A (emotional support) or Hypothesis 3B (instrumental support). Substantively, affordability continues to function as the dominant structural constraint, while partner support correlates with higher overall employment probabilities but does not alter the affordability-employment relationship.

To test **Hypothesis 4**, we estimated a logistic regression model examining whether the effect of perceived childcare affordability on maternal employment is moderated by the mother's relative contribution to household income. Table 16 presents the results of the model, and Figure 10 visualizes the interaction using predicted probabilities across varying levels of affordability and income share.

The results in Table 16 show that mothers' relative income contribution is positively associated with employment ($\beta = 0.208, p < 0.01$), indicating that women who contribute a larger share to the household income are more likely to be in paid work. Crucially, the interaction term between perceived affordability and the mother's income share is negative and statistically significant ($\beta =$

-0.032, $p < 0.01$), suggesting that the negative relationship between affordability and employment is attenuated at higher levels of female income contribution. In other words, the affordability-employment link is stronger for mothers with lower income shares, and weaker or absent among those who are primary or sole earners.

Table 16. *Logistic Regression: Employment on Affordability x Mother's Income Share*

	(1) Model 1
Mother is Employed	
Perceived Affordability	-1.612*** (0.420)
Mother's share of income	0.208*** (0.057)
Perceived Affordability# Mother's share of income	-0.032*** (0.011)
Constant	6.102** (2.650)

* $p < 0.1$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$

Notes: Controls included: age, education, rural/urban, household income (not shown for brevity).

To visualize the interaction, Figure 10 plots predicted probabilities of employment at different levels of affordability, holding income share at four values (-25, 0, 25, 50). These values are centered around 50%, such that -25 \approx 25% of household income, 0 \approx 50%, 25 \approx 75%, and 50 \approx 100%.

Top-left panel (my_share_c = -25): This group represents mothers who earn approximately 25% of the total household income. Here, the graph shows a clear negative slope: as perceived childcare affordability worsens (from "Affordable" to "Unaffordable"), the predicted probability of being employed drops substantially, from roughly 0.9 to below 0.6. This indicates a strong sensitivity to affordability among financially dependent mothers.

Top-right panel (my_share_c = 0): For mothers who earn equally to their partners (50%), the negative slope remains visible but is less pronounced. The predicted probability declines moderately with reduced affordability, suggesting that even among egalitarian couples, cost barriers continue to matter.

Bottom-left panel (my_share_c = 25): When the mother earns about 75% of the household income, the predicted employment probability remains relatively stable across all affordability levels, only

slightly declining from high to low affordability. This implies that mothers with higher economic contribution are less deterred by cost constraints.

Bottom-right panel (my_share_c = 50): For mothers who are the sole or primary breadwinners, the employment probability is consistently high across all levels of perceived affordability (approximately 0.9), with no visible sensitivity to affordability barriers. This suggests that when economic responsibility falls primarily on the mother, employment is likely maintained regardless of external childcare costs.

Figure 10. Interaction of Childcare Affordability and Mother’s Income Share on Employment

The results support Hypothesis 4. Perceived affordability negatively affects maternal employment, but this effect is conditioned by the mother’s relative economic position within the household. Mothers who are less financially empowered are more likely to withdraw from employment when faced with unaffordable childcare. Conversely, those who earn the majority or all of the household income appear insulated from affordability barriers, likely due to economic necessity or greater bargaining power.

7.2 Factorial Survey Experiment Results

Table 17 reports the results of the factorial survey experiment, estimated with mixed-effects linear regression models with random intercepts at the respondent level (see Sections 5.4 and 5.7 for details on vignette design, measurement, and analytical strategy).

Table 17. Factorial Survey Models

	(1) Support for mother returning to work	(2) Preferred maternal work hours	(3) Preferred childcare hours
Child age: 1	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
Child age: 5	0.564*** (7.12)	0.603*** (10.44)	0.421*** (9.17)
High support	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
Low help	-0.144 (-1.46)	-0.302*** (-4.19)	-0.114* (-1.98)
Prefers she stays home	-0.0752 (-0.79)	-0.212** (-3.08)	-0.148** (-2.68)
Remote	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
9–17 fixed	-0.189* (-2.01)	-0.0463 (-0.68)	0.0895 (1.65)
Shift work	-0.373*** (-3.80)	-0.212** (-2.97)	-0.0415 (-0.72)
€70 subsidy, €80 fee, €350 income	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
€0 subsidy, €150 fee, €550 income	0.0191 (0.21)	-0.159* (-2.42)	-0.0187 (-0.35)
€0 subsidy, €150 fee, €750 income	0.125 (1.34)	0.0538 (0.79)	0.0984 (1.82)
Constant	3.754*** (31.05)	3.173*** (33.40)	2.917*** (38.62)
Ins1_1_1			
Constant	-0.168** (-2.59)	-0.190*** (-3.42)	-0.442*** (-7.81)
Insig_e			
Constant	-0.103** (-3.15)	-0.453*** (-13.83)	-0.676*** (-20.59)
Observations	710	706	704

t statistics in parentheses * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$

Child Age: Across all three outcomes, the age of the child in the vignette has a strong and statistically significant effect. Compared to a one-year-old child (reference), a five-year-old child increases support for maternal employment by 0.564 points ($p < 0.001$), increases the preferred number of work hours by 0.603 points ($p < 0.001$), and raises the preferred number of childcare hours by 0.421 points ($p < 0.001$). These findings suggest that maternal employment is considered more acceptable as children grow older, consistent with widely held developmental assumptions and previous research on age-related norms.

Partner Support: Partner support is another consistent predictor across models. Respondents who read vignettes where the partner offers only limited help (versus high support) express significantly lower preferences for maternal work hours ($-0.302, p < 0.001$) and childcare hours ($-0.114, p < 0.05$), although the effect on support for returning to work is negative but not statistically significant. When the partner explicitly prefers the mother to stay home, support further declines, significantly reducing preferred work hours ($-0.212, p < 0.01$) and childcare hours ($-0.148, p < 0.01$), but again with a non-significant effect on general support for return to work. These results imply that normative expectations are sensitive to household dynamics, especially when maternal labor market participation contradicts perceived partner preferences.

Work Flexibility: Compared to flexible remote work, shift work is associated with lower support for return to work ($-0.373, p < 0.001$) and preferred work hours ($-0.212, p < 0.01$), likely due to the time strain and unpredictability shift work imposes on family life. Fixed full-time work (9-17) has a smaller but significant negative effect on support for return to work ($-0.189, p < 0.05$), though it does not significantly affect preferred work or childcare hours. This suggests that full-time but stable schedules are perceived more favorably than shift-based work, but still somewhat less desirable than flexible options.

Childcare Affordability: A key objective of this vignette experiment was to assess whether public attitudes differ in response to a targeted childcare subsidy, modeled after the Prishtina Municipality's €70 childcare subsidy for low-income families. In the vignette design, this condition was represented by a household with €350 income, €70 subsidy, and an €80 net childcare fee and served as the reference category in the regression models.

Compared to this subsidized condition, the other two conditions which offered no subsidy, a higher childcare fee (€150), and higher household incomes (€550 or €750) did not significantly increase

public support for a mother's return to work or preferred childcare hours. In fact, the medium-income condition (€550) significantly reduced the preferred maternal work hours (-0.159, $p < 0.05$), suggesting that even modestly higher fees without subsidy may dampen normative support for maternal employment. The high-income condition (€750) slightly increased preferred childcare hours (+0.098, $p = 0.069$), but the effect was only marginal.

Taken together, these results suggest that a targeted childcare subsidy like the one offered in Prishtina may help normalize and support maternal employment, especially for low-income families. That this subsidized condition was consistently rated more favorably than costlier, unsubsidized alternatives, even when household income was higher, signals potential public endorsement of redistributive childcare policies aimed at easing access for disadvantaged households.

Intercept and Random Effects

The constant terms in all models are large and significant, reflecting the overall favorable attitudes toward mothers' return to work (mean = 3.75), moderate preferences for maternal working hours (mean = 3.17), and slightly lower preferences for childcare hours (mean = 2.92). The variance components suggest meaningful between-respondent differences, justifying the use of random effects. Likelihood ratio tests against linear models confirm that the mixed-effects specifications significantly improve model fit ($p < 0.001$ in all cases).

In summary, the results provide strong support for **Hypothesis 5A** and **Hypothesis 5C**, demonstrating that both the age of the child and the flexibility of the mother's job shape public support for maternal employment and childcare use. Specifically, respondents expressed higher normative approval when the child was five years old and when the job offered remote work rather than shift-based or fixed hours. **Hypothesis 5B** received partial support: while limited partner help or explicit opposition reduced preferred work and childcare hours, it did not significantly affect overall support for returning to work. **Hypothesis 5D** was also only partially supported. Although the subsidized childcare condition, modeled after the Prishtina Municipality program consistently produced more favorable attitudes, most differences relative to higher-income, unsubsidized conditions were not statistically significant. Overall, the factorial survey findings suggest that both household dynamics and policy-relevant contextual factors influence normative expectations surrounding maternal employment, but that the strength of these effects varies across dimensions.

8 Discussion and Conclusion

This thesis examined how childcare accessibility and social norms shape maternal employment in Kosovo, using a dual design that combined a cross-sectional survey with a factorial survey experiment (FSE). The discussion synthesizes the findings, situates them within existing theory and international research, and outlines policy implications and limitations.

Mothers perceiving childcare as unaffordable were significantly less likely to be employed, even after adjusting for socio-demographic and economic controls, whereas perceptions of availability and quality had no independent effects. In low-income contexts such as Kosovo, affordability functions as the primary threshold. When childcare is prohibitively expensive relative to household income, families cannot meaningfully prioritize quality or ease of access, since the service itself is out of reach. By contrast, in high-income countries where affordability barriers are reduced, parents are able to weigh dimensions such as quality or proximity more strongly. This helps explain why only affordability emerged as significant in the Kosovo case. This finding diverges from evidence in high-income countries, where availability (Brilli et al., 2016) or quality (Schober & Spiess, 2015) often plays a stronger role. These results resonate more closely with findings from post-socialist and Southern European contexts (Lovász, 2016; Bouchard et al., 2021), where cost sensitivity has been shown to dominate childcare decision-making. In such contexts, fragmented provision and a reliance on private or semi-private centers mean that services exist but remain inaccessible for large segments of the population. This helps explain why respondents in Kosovo did not report availability or ease of finding childcare as major barriers: when centers are primarily market-driven, places can technically be found, but at a price point that excludes many families.

Beyond structural constraints, this thesis also investigated the role of social norms. Contrary to expectations, the cross-sectional analysis showed no mediating effect of descriptive norms, prescriptive norms, or gender-essentialist beliefs on the affordability-employment relationship. However, this “null finding” must be interpreted with caution. Survey responses about gender attitudes are vulnerable to social desirability bias, and the cross-sectional design may not fully capture the complexity of normative influence.

The factorial survey experiment (FSE) offered additional insights by probing normative expectations in hypothetical but realistic scenarios. Here, clear patterns emerged: approval of maternal employment was higher when children were older, when jobs were flexible, when

partners were supportive, and when childcare was subsidized. These results suggest that while affordability constrains actual behavior, norms continue to shape the perceived legitimacy of maternal employment. The divergence between the cross-sectional and experimental findings underscores the importance of methodological triangulation: conventional surveys may underestimate normative effects, whereas vignette experiments can reveal latent expectations that are not easily captured through direct questioning. While norms did not statistically mediate the affordability-employment relationship in the cross-sectional models, the factorial survey results demonstrate that norms continue to matter at the level of public attitudes and legitimacy. This distinction between behavioral constraints and normative ideals is central to interpreting the findings.

The analysis of moderating mechanisms further enriches this picture. Partner support, both emotional and instrumental, was positively associated with maternal employment overall, but it did not significantly condition the affordability-employment link. This indicates that supportive partners can create a favorable baseline for women's labor force participation, yet they cannot offset the structural barrier posed by high childcare costs. By contrast, mothers' relative contribution to household income strongly moderated the affordability effect. Women with lower income shares were highly sensitive to childcare costs, whereas those who were primary earners were less affected. This aligns with bargaining theories of intra-household decision-making, which argue that women's employment prospects depend not only on external structures but also on their economic leverage within the household.

Together, these findings point to several policy implications. First, reducing childcare costs, through subsidies, sliding-scale fees, or expansion of public provision, emerges as the most direct lever for enabling maternal employment. Second, targeted subsidy programs, such as the Prishtina Municipality's €70 initiative, may be especially impactful, both materially and normatively, as they lower barriers while also signaling institutional support for working mothers. Third, policies that enhance women's independent earning capacity, such as promoting flexible and decent part-time jobs, strengthening fathers' leave entitlements, and investing in women's career continuity, can reduce the disproportionate vulnerability of economically dependent mothers.

Limitations. While this study makes several contributions, it is not without limitations. First, the sample included only a small number of fathers, limiting the ability to draw conclusions about

paternal perspectives or household bargaining from both sides. Second, survey dropout was a non-negligible issue: several respondents did not complete the questionnaire, often due to its length, and attrition was particularly pronounced among male participants. This raises concerns about potential bias, as those with lower education levels or limited digital literacy may have been more likely to discontinue. Relatedly, although purposive sampling via Facebook groups and NGO networks enabled access to parents of young children, it may have overrepresented digitally connected, more educated households, thereby limiting generalizability to the broader population of Kosovo. Another limitation relates to the measurement of social norms. Responses on normative attitudes are vulnerable to social desirability bias: participants may have downplayed traditional beliefs or overstated egalitarian views in order to present themselves as more progressive. If this bias is present, the non-significant mediation effects observed could partly reflect underreporting of conservative attitudes rather than a genuine lack of normative influence.

Future Research. Future studies could build on this work in several ways. First, longitudinal designs would allow for stronger causal claims about how affordability shapes employment trajectories. Second, extending analysis to fathers' roles and preferences could shed light on how gendered divisions of labor evolve. Third, comparative studies across the Western Balkans would clarify whether Kosovo represents an extreme case or reflects broader regional patterns. Finally, experimental interventions, such as randomized subsidies or norm-change campaigns, could more directly test causal mechanisms.

Conclusion. Taken together, the findings point to early signs that social norms in Kosovo may be shifting toward greater acceptance of maternal employment, at least in principle. The factorial survey results showed that respondents were more supportive of working mothers under favorable conditions, suggesting that traditional constraints are less rigid than often assumed. Yet, given the risk of social desirability bias noted earlier, these normative shifts should be interpreted cautiously: they may reflect aspirational ideals as much as lived realities. What is clear, however, is that affordability continues to act as the bottleneck through which all other mechanisms must pass. This highlights a paradox of change: while attitudes appear to be evolving, structural barriers especially high childcare costs still prevent these attitudes from materializing in practice. Addressing affordability could therefore serve a dual function: enabling women's employment directly and accelerating the alignment between changing norms and everyday behavior.

References

- Addati, L., Cattaneo, U., & Pozzan, E. (2022). *Care at work: Investing in care leave and services for a more gender-equal world of work*. International Labour Office.
<https://doi.org/10.54394/AQOF1491>
- Andringa, W., Nieuwenhuis, R., & Van Gerven, M. (2015). Women's working hours: the interplay between gender role attitudes, motherhood, and public childcare support in 23 European countries *In: The International Journal of Sociology and Social Policy, Vol. 35, No. 9/10, 2015, 582-599* <https://search.gesis.org/publication/iab-litdok-K150914801>
- Assembly of Kosovo. (2006). *Law No. 02/L-52 on Preschool Education*. Official Gazette of the Provisional Institutions of Self-Government in Kosovo, 1 June 2006.
- Assembly of the Republic of Kosovo. (2010). *Law No. 03/L-212 on Labour*. Official Gazette of the Republic of Kosovo, No. 90, 1 December 2010. <https://gzk.rks-gov.net/ActDetail.aspx?ActID=2735&langid=2>
- Assembly of the Republic of Kosovo. (2023). *Law No. 08/L-153 on Early Childhood Education*. Official Gazette of the Republic of Kosovo, 17, 3 August 2023.
- Auspurg, K., & Hinz, T. (2015). Factorial survey experiments. In *SAGE Publications, Inc. eBooks*. <https://doi.org/10.4135/9781483398075>
- A European Care Strategy for caregivers and care receivers*. (2022, September 7). Employment, Social Affairs and Inclusion. https://employment-social-affairs.ec.europa.eu/news/european-care-strategy-caregivers-and-care-receivers-2022-09-07_en?utm_source
- Bartlett, W., & Uvalić, M. (2022). Introduction: social protection in the Western Balkans. *Journal of International and Comparative Social Policy, 38(2)*, 130-134.
<https://doi.org/10.1017/ics.2022.10>
- Bauernschuster, S., & Schlotter, M. (2015). Public child care and mothers' labor supply - Evidence from two quasi-experiments. *Journal of Public Economics, 123*, 1–16.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpubeco.2014.12.013>
- Becker, G. (1976) *The Economic Approach to Human Behavior*. University of Chicago Press, Chicago.
- Behrami, M., Pacolli, F., & Ramqaj, F. (2020). *Why is early education the solution?* Friedrich-Ebert-Stiftung, Prishtina Office. <https://library.fes.de/pdf-files/bueros/kosovo/16273-20201022.pdf>
- Bicchieri, C. (2017). *Norms in the wild: How to diagnose, measure, and change social norms*. Oxford University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1093/acprof:oso/9780190622046.001.0001>

- Bouchard, I., Cheung, L., & Pacheco, G. (2020). Evaluating the impact of 20 hours free early childhood education on mothers' labour force participation and earnings. *New Zealand Economic Papers*, 55(2), 188–202. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00779954.2020.1791941>
- Brilli, Y., Del Boca, D., & Pronzato, C. D. (2016). Does child care availability play a role in maternal employment and children's development? Evidence from Italy. *Review of Economics of the Household*, 14(1), 27–51. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11150-013-9227-4>
- Bröckel, M. (2016). The role of partners' support for women's reentry into employment after a Child-Related career break in Germany. *Journal of Family Issues*, 39(7), 1739-1769. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0192513x16653435>
- Chung, H., & van der Horst, M. (2018). Women's employment patterns after childbirth and the perceived access to and use of flexitime and teleworking. *Human relations; studies towards the integration of the social sciences*, 71(1), 47-72. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0018726717713828>
- Council of the European Union. (2022, December 8). Council recommendation on early childhood education and care: The Barcelona targets for 2030 (2022/C 484/01). Official Journal of the European Union, C 484, 1-9. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32022H1208%2801%29>
- Demas, A., Aliu, M., Coll-Black, S., Zafeirakou, A., Hankey, A., Gotcheva, B., & WORLD BANK GROUP. (2021). A situational analysis of early Childhood development (ECD) services in Kosovo. International Bank for Reconstruction and Development / The World Bank. <https://documents1.worldbank.org/curated/en/896121631867828915/pdf/A-Situational-Analysis-of-Early-Childhood-Development-ECD-Services-in-Kosovo.pdf>
- Dobrotić, I. (2022). Challenges to the Europeanisation of work-care policies in the Western Balkans. *Journal of International and Comparative Social Policy*, 38(2), 165–179. <https://doi.org/10.1017/ics.2022.7>
- Drevinja, M., Ymeri, V., & UBO Consulting. (2022). *Who cares? unpaid care work in Kosovo* [Report]. <https://musineinstitute.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/11/07-Who-Cares-ENG08.pdf>
- Esping-Andersen, G. (1990). The three worlds of welfare capitalism.
- Frodermann, C., Hipp, L., & Bünning, M. (2024). Money matters! Evidence from a survey experiment on attitudes toward maternal employment across contexts in Germany. *Gender & Society*, 38(3), 436-465. <https://doi.org/10.1177/08912432241252601>
- Gaunt, R. (2006). Biological essentialism, gender ideologies, and role attitudes: What determines parents' involvement in child care. *Sex Roles*, 55(7–8), 523–533. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11199-006-9105-0>

- Gjelaj, M., Rraci, E., & Bajrami, K. (2018). *Pre-school education in Kosovo*. Kosovo Education and Employment Network (KEEN). https://www.researchgate.net/publication/334896051_PRE-SCHOOL_EDUCATION_IN_KOSOVO
- Goldscheider, F., Bernhardt, E., & Lappegård, T. (2015). The Gender Revolution: a framework for understanding changing family and demographic behavior. *Population and Development Review*, 41(2), 207–239. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1728-4457.2015.00045.x>
- Greenhaus, J. H., & Beutell, N. J. (1985). Sources of Conflict between Work and Family Roles. *The Academy of Management Review*, 10(1), 76-88. <https://doi.org/10.2307/258214>
- Greenhaus, J. H., & Powell, G. N. (2006). When work and family are allies: A theory of work-family enrichment. *Academy of Management Review*, 31(1), 72-92. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/20159186>
- Hermes, H., Krauß, M., Lergetporer, P., Peter, F., & Wiederhold, S. (2024). The causal impact of gender norms on mothers' employment attitudes and expectations. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.5065248>
- Ingenfeld, J. (2021). Mothers' Employment Participation: the role of partner involvement and selection processes. *Journal of Marriage and Family*, 83(4), 1020-1037. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jomf.12755>
- Klenk, T., & Reiter, R. (2023). Social services as critical infrastructure – conceptualising and studying the operational core of the social investment state. *European Journal of Social Security*, 25(2), 115-138. <https://doi.org/10.1177/13882627231175566> (Original work published 2023)
- Lind, Y. (2021). Childcare infrastructure in the Nordic countries as a way of enabling female labor market participation. *National Tax Journal*, 74(4), 1005-1032. <https://doi.org/10.1086/717989>
- Lovász, A. (2016). Childcare expansion and mothers' employment in post-socialist countries. *IZA World of Labor*, 319. <https://doi.org/10.15185/izawol.319>
- Lundberg, S., & Pollak, R. A. (1996). Bargaining and Distribution in Marriage. *The Journal of Economic Perspectives*, 10(4), 139–158. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/2138558>
- Merton, R. K. (1968). The Matthew effect in science. *Science*, 159(3810), 56-63. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.159.3810.56>
- Ministry of Education, Science, Technology, and Innovation (MESTI). (2022). *Education Strategy 2022–2026*. <https://masht.rks-gov.net/wp-content/uploads/2022/11/03-Strategja-e-Arsimit-2022-2026-Eng-Web.pdf>

- Moriconi, Simone; Rodríguez-Planas, Núria (2021): Gender Norms and the Motherhood Employment Gap, IZA Discussion Papers, No. 14898, Institute of Labor Economics (IZA), Bonn <https://www.econstor.eu/bitstream/10419/250559/1/dp14898.pdf>
- Mustafa, A. (2021). Early Childhood Education and Care in Kosovo: A targeted educational approach producing and maintaining social and gender inequalities. *Revija Za Socijalnu Politiku*, 27(3), 367–390. <https://doi.org/10.3935/rsp.v28i3.1808>
- OECD (2023), *Joining Forces for Gender Equality: What is Holding us Back?*, OECD Publishing, Paris, <https://doi.org/10.1787/67d48024-en>.
- OECD. (2023). *OECD Family database*. https://www.oecd.org/els/family/LMF1_2_Maternal_Employment.pdf
- Olivetti, C., & Petrongolo, B. (2017). The Economic Consequences of Family Policies: Lessons from a Century of Legislation in High-Income Countries. *The Journal of Economic Perspectives*, 31(1), 205-230. <https://doi.org/10.1257/jep.31.1.205>
- Ruppanner, L., Collins, C., Landivar, L. C., & Scarborough, W. J. (2021). How do Gender Norms and Childcare Costs Affect Maternal Employment Across US States? *Gender & Society*, 35(6), 910–939. <https://doi.org/10.1177/08912432211046988>
- Sani, G. M. D., & Scherer, S. (2017). Maternal Employment: Enabling Factors in context. *Work Employment and Society*, 32(1), 75–92. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0950017016677944>
- Schober, P. S., & Spiess, C. K. (2015). Local day care quality and maternal employment: Evidence from East and West Germany. *Journal of Marriage and Family*, 77(3), 712–729. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jomf.12180>
- Sedlander, E., Bingenheimer, J. B., Long, M. W., Swain, M., & Rimal, R. N. (2022). The G-NORM Scale: Development and Validation of a Theory-Based Gender Norms Scale. *Sex roles*, 87(5-6), 350-363. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11199-022-01319-9>
- UN Women. (2024). *Kosovo gender country profile*. Pristina: UN Women Kosovo Office. Funded by the European Union. <https://eca.unwomen.org/en/digital-library/publications/2024/11/kosovo-gender-country-profile>
- Zangger, C., Widmer, J., & Gilgen, S. (2021). Work, childcare, or both? Experimental evidence on the efficacy of childcare subsidies in raising parental labor supply. *Journal of Family and Economic Issues*, 42(3), 449-472. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10834-020-09749-x>
- Zoch, G., & Hondralis, I. (2017). The expansion of low-cost, state-subsidized childcare availability and mothers' return-to-work behaviour in East and West Germany. *European Sociological Review*, 33(5), 693–707. <https://doi.org/10.1093/esr/jcx068>

Appendix A: Full Survey Instrument (Cross-Sectional & Factorial Survey)

Welcome, and thank you for taking the time to participate in this survey!

This study is part of my Master's thesis in *Public Policy and Social Change* at the University of Tübingen, Germany, supervised by Prof. Dr. Pia Schober and Dr. Volker Lang. My name is Diellza Veliu, and through this research, I aim to better understand how the availability, affordability, and quality of early childhood education and care (ECEC) services in Kosovo influence women's ability to participate in the labor market. The study also explores how family dynamics and social expectations, such as support from partners or societal norms, shape mothers' decisions about returning to work. This survey is intended for parents or guardians who currently have at least one child under the age of 6. The survey takes approximately 10-12 minutes to complete. Participation is entirely voluntary, and all responses will be treated with strict confidentiality and used solely for academic research purposes.

PART 1: Cross-Sectional Questionnaire

SECTION 1: Socioeconomic Background

To begin, we'd like to ask you a few questions about yourself, your household, and your current work situation.

Q1. What is your gender?

Female

Male

Other

Prefer not to say

Q2. How old are you?

[Open numeric field]

Q3. In which region of Kosovo do you currently live?

Prishtinë

Mitrovicë

Pejë

Gjakovë

Prizren

Ferizaj

Gjilan

Q4. How would you describe the area where you live?

Urban (city or town)

Rural (village or countryside)

Q5. What is the highest level of education you have completed?

- No formal education
- Primary school (class 1-5)
- Lower secondary school (class 6-9)
- Upper secondary school (class 10-12)
- Bachelor's degree
- Master's degree
- Doctoral degree (PhD)
- Prefer not to say

Q6. What is your ethnic background? (Note: Please choose the group you identify with most)

- Albanian
- Ashkali
- Egyptian
- Roma
- Bosniak
- Other (please specify):
- Prefer not to say

Q7. Do you have any children under the age of 6?

- Yes
- No → *[If selected, survey ends here with a thank-you message]*

Q7a. In total, how many children under the age of 18 live in your household?

- [Open numeric field]

Q8. What is your current employment status?

- Employed full-time
- Employed part-time
- Self-employed
- Employed but currently on maternity leave
- Unemployed (less than 12 months)
- Unemployed (12 months or more)
- Homemaker / Full-time caregiver
- Student/in education
- Other

[Skip logic: If respondent selects "Employed full-time," "Employed part-time," "Self-employed," or "Employed but currently on maternity leave" → Skip to Q8b

If any other option is selected → Proceed to Q8a

Q8a. What are the main reasons you are currently not in paid employment? *(Multiple Choice)*

- I am undergoing education or training
- I have a long-term illness or disability
- I am doing housework or caring for children or other persons
- I do not want to work at this time
- I would like to work but cannot find a suitable job
- Another reason (please specify): _____

Q8b. Regardless of your basic or contracted hours, how many hours {do/did} you normally work a week (in your main job), including any paid or unpaid overtime.

(Note: If on maternity leave, report your usual weekly hours before the leave.)

[Open numeric field]

- Prefer not to say

Q9. Please can you tell me how much your household's NET income per MONTH is?

(Note: By "net income," we mean the total amount your household receives each month after taxes and social contributions have been deducted).

[Open numeric field]

- Prefer not to say

If left blank or "prefer not to say", the following question appears:

Q9a. If you prefer not to provide an exact amount, please indicate the approximate range of your total monthly household income (net):

- Less than €500
- €501-700
- €701-900
- €901-1,100
- €1,101-1,300
- €1,301-1,500
- More than €1,500
- Prefer not to say

Q9b. Approximately what percentage of your household's total monthly income comes from you personally?

If you are not sure, please give your best estimate.

[Open numeric field: ____ %]

- Prefer not to say

Q10. Considering all sources of income, between you and your spouse/ partner, who has the higher income?

- No partner
- My spouse/ partner has no income
- I have a much higher income
- I have a higher income
- We have about the same income
- My spouse/ partner has a higher income
- My spouse/ partner has a much higher income
- I have no income
- No answer

SECTION 2: Childcare Accessibility

The next section asks about your current childcare arrangements and how accessible childcare services are in your area.

Q11. What is the main type of childcare your youngest child (under age 6) currently receives?
(Multiple choice)

- Public kindergarten or preschool
- Private kindergarten or preschool
- Community-based childcare (e.g., NGO-run)
- Pre-primary education in public school (age 5–6)
- Pre-primary education in private school (age 5–6)
- Cared for by mother at home
- Cared for by father at home
- Cared for by grandparent(s)
- Cared for by other relatives/friends/neighbors (informal)
- Other (please specify): _____

[Skip logic: Only show Q12 + Q12a + Q13 if respondent selects one of the following options in Q11:

- *Public kindergarten or preschool*
- *Private kindergarten or preschool*
- *Community-based childcare (e.g., NGO-run)*
- *Pre-primary education in public school (age 5–6)*
- *Pre-primary education in private school (age 5–6)*

If any other option is selected, skip to Q14.]

Q12. Approximately how many hours per week does your youngest child attend this formal childcare or early education service?

Note: Please include only the time spent in the childcare facility (not transport or time at home).

[Open numeric field]

Q12a. How much do you currently pay per month for this childcare service?

€ [Open numeric field]

Q13. On a scale from 1 to 5, how satisfied are you with the following aspects of your current childcare service? (1 = Very dissatisfied, 5 = Very satisfied)

	1	2	3	4	5
Q13a. Quality of the facilities (building, room, equipment)	<input type="radio"/>				
Q13b. The number of children per group/class	<input type="radio"/>				
Q13c. Expertise and professionalism of staff/carers	<input type="radio"/>				
Q13d. Personal attention the child was given, including staff/carers' attitude and time devoted	<input type="radio"/>				
Q13e. Being informed or consulted about the child's care	<input type="radio"/>				
Q13f. The curriculum and activities	<input type="radio"/>				

Q14. Thinking about the overall affordability of childcare provided in your local area, for a family like yours how good would you say this is?

Very good

Fairly good

Adequate

Fairly poor

Very poor

Q15. How easy or difficult is it for you to find a childcare provider near your home that can accommodate your child's special educational or health needs?

Very easy

Easy

Neither easy nor difficult

Difficult

Very difficult

Q16. Thinking about the overall number of places at formal childcare providers in your local area, would you say that there are currently:

Far too many places

Slightly too many places

About the right number of places

Slightly too few places

Far too few places

Q17. Thinking about the overall quality of childcare provided in your local area, would you say this is:

- Very good
- Fairly good
- Adequate
- Fairly poor
- Very poor

SECTION 3: Social Norms & Partner Support & Gender Essentialism

In this section, we'll ask about everyday roles, responsibilities, and beliefs in your household and your community. We are interested in your views on how tasks and decisions are typically shared between partners, and what is commonly expected of mothers and fathers.

Descriptive norms (What people *typically* do in families you know)

Q18. On a scale from 1 to 5, to what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements? (1 = Strongly disagree, 5 = Strongly agree)

In most families that I know...	1	2	3	4	5
Q18a. ...taking care of children is only the woman's job.	<input type="radio"/>				
Q18b. ... only men are the ones who earn money for the family.	<input type="radio"/>				
Q18c. ...mothers of young children usually stay home rather than work.	<input type="radio"/>				

Prescriptive norms (What people *believe should* happen in families you know)

Q19. On a scale from 1 to 5, to what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements? (1 = Strongly disagree, 5 = Strongly agree)

Most families that I know believe that...	1	2	3	4	5
Q19a. ...it <i>should</i> only be a woman's job to take care of the children.	<input type="radio"/>				
Q19b. ...men <i>should</i> be the only ones who earn money for the family.	<input type="radio"/>				
Q19c. ... mothers of young children <i>should</i> stay home rather than work.	<input type="radio"/>				

Q20. The next questions are about who does what in your household. Please indicate who does the following tasks in your household.

Task	Always me	Usually me	Shared equally	Usually my partner	Always my partner	Someone else	Prefer not to say
Q20a. Doing the laundry	<input type="radio"/>						
Q20b. Making small repairs in or around the house	<input type="radio"/>						

Q20c. Caring for sick family members	<input type="radio"/>						
Q20d. Shopping for groceries	<input type="radio"/>						
Q20e. Cleaning the house	<input type="radio"/>						
Q20f. Preparing meals	<input type="radio"/>						

Q21. The next statements are about various tasks that have to be done when one lives together with children. Please indicate, who in your household does these tasks?

Task	Always me	Usually me	Shared equally	Usually my partner	Always my partner	Someone else	Prefer not to say
Q21a. Dressing the children or seeing that the children are properly dressed	<input type="radio"/>						
Q21b. Staying at home with the children when they are ill	<input type="radio"/>						
Q21c. Playing with the children and/or taking part in leisure activities with them	<input type="radio"/>						
Q21d. Putting the children to bed	<input type="radio"/>						
Q21e. Helping the children with homework	<input type="radio"/>						

Q22. How satisfied are you with the following aspects of the division of responsibilities between you and your partner?

Please rate each item on a scale from 1 to 5 where: 1 = Very dissatisfied... 5 = Very satisfied

Statement	1	2	3	4	5	Not applicable / No partner
Q22a. How satisfied are you with the way household tasks are divided between you and your partner?	<input type="radio"/>					
Q22a. How satisfied are you with the way childcare responsibilities are shared between you and your partner?	<input type="radio"/>					

Q23. Who usually makes decisions about the following issues in your household?

Please select the option that best describes who has the most say in each case.

Issue	Always me	Usually me	Equally me and my partner	Usually my partner	Always my partner	Someone else
Q23a. The time you spend in paid work	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Q23b. The time your partner spends in paid work	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Q24. To what extent do you agree with the following statements about your partner's emotional support? (1 = Not at all ... 5 = Very much)

Statement	1	2	3	4	5	Not applicable / No partner
Q24a. My partner encourages me to pursue my own career goals.	<input type="radio"/>					
Q24b. My partner supports my decisions about using formal childcare (e.g., kindergartens, nurseries).	<input type="radio"/>					

Q25. To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements?

Please use a scale from 1 to 5, where:

1 = Strongly Disagree... 5 = Strongly Agree

Statement	1	2	3	4	5
Q25a. Mothers are instinctively better caretakers than fathers.	<input type="radio"/>				
Q25b. Mothers are naturally more sensitive to a baby's feelings than fathers are.	<input type="radio"/>				
Q25c. In terms of childcare, fathers have to learn what mothers are able to do naturally.	<input type="radio"/>				

PART 2: Factorial Survey Experiment

Introductory Text of the Vignette Module:

In the next section, you will be presented with three hypothetical short stories about a woman named Arta and her family. Each story describes a different everyday situation that Arta and her partner might face. After each story, we will ask you a few short questions about what you think Arta should do. There are no right or wrong answers, we are only interested in your personal opinion.

Arta and her partner live together with their child. She is currently not working and is considering returning to work. At the moment...

Dimensions	Levels		
Child's age	Their child is 1 year old. (1)	Their child is 5-year-old. (2)	
Partner support	Arta's partner fully supports her return to work and regularly helps with housework and childcare. (1)	Arta's partner supports her return to work, but rarely helps with housework or childcare. (2)	Arta's partner would prefer that she stays home to care for the child. (3)
Work Flexibility	Arta is considering a job that allows her to work remotely most of the time from home. (1)	Arta is considering a job that has fixed working hours from 9:00 to 17:00. (2)	Arta is considering a job that involves shift work, with rotating early, late, or night shifts. (3)
Childcare Affordability	The couple's household income is €350 per month. They receive a €70 childcare subsidy and pay €80 per month for private kindergarten. (1)	The couple's household income is €550 per month. They do not receive any subsidy and pay €150 per month for private kindergarten. (2)	The couple's household income is €750 per month. They do not receive any subsidy and pay €150 per month for private kindergarten. (3)

Q26. Based on the situation described, do you think Arta should return to work full-time?

Definitely not

Probably not

Not sure

Probably yes

Definitely yes

Q27. If Arta does return to work, how many hours per week do you think would be appropriate for her to work?

0 hours (stay at home)

Less than 20 hours

20-29 hours

30-39 hours

40 or more hours

Q28. Given this situation, how much time should Arta's child spend in formal childcare each day?

None, the child should be cared for at home

A few hours on selected days

Half day, every day

Full day, every day

Appendix B. Regional Distribution of Respondents

Table B1. Sample distribution of respondents by region

Region	Freq.	Percent	Cum.
Prishtinë	112	46.47	46.47
Mitrovicë	25	10.37	56.85
Pejë	15	6.22	63.07
Gjakovë	10	4.15	67.22
Prizren	14	5.81	73.03
Ferizaj	28	11.62	84.65
Gjilan	35	14.52	99.17
.	2	0.83	100.00
Total	241	100.00	

Source: Author's survey data (N=241).

Table B2. Population distribution of Kosovo by region (2022)

Region	Population
Prishtinë	490,273
Mitrovicë	224,121
Pejë	222,751
Gjakovë	215,025
Prizren	292,597
Ferizaj	185,119
Gjilan	168,302
Total	1,798,188

Source: Kosovo Agency of Statistics (KAS), 2022 population estimates.

Each region's share:

- Prishtinë: $490,273 / 1,798,188 \times 100 \approx 27.3\%$
- Mitrovicë: $224,121 / 1,798,188 \times 100 \approx 12.5\%$
- Pejë: $222,751 / 1,798,188 \times 100 \approx 12.4\%$
- Gjakovë: $215,025 / 1,798,188 \times 100 \approx 12.0\%$
- Prizren: $292,597 / 1,798,188 \times 100 \approx 16.3\%$
- Ferizaj: $185,119 / 1,798,188 \times 100 \approx 10.3\%$
- Gjilan: $168,302 / 1,798,188 \times 100 \approx 9.4\%$

The two tables compare the regional distribution of survey respondents with Kosovo's population distribution. The sample is not strictly proportional to the population: respondents from Prishtinë (46.5%) and Gjilan (14.5%) are overrepresented relative to their population shares (27.3% and 9.4%, respectively), while Prizren, Gjakovë, and Pejë are underrepresented. This imbalance reflects recruitment dynamics and the relative accessibility of participants in certain regions. Since the study does not aim for a nationally representative sample but rather explores mechanisms related to childcare and maternal employment, these deviations do not compromise the validity of the analyses. The comparison is included for transparency.

Appendix C: Division of Housework and Childcare Tasks by Gender

Table C1: Reported Division of Childcare Tasks - Female Respondents (N = 216)

Task	Always Me	Usually Me	Shared Equally	Usually Partner	Always Partner
Dressing children	43.1%	26.9%	27.3%	0.9%	0.9%
Staying home when child is ill	44.4%	30.1%	22.2%	-	1.9%
Playing with children	16.2%	22.7%	56.0%	2.8%	0.5%
Putting children to bed	43.5%	26.9%	25.5%	1.9%	0.9%
Helping with homework	25.9%	23.1%	42.6%	0.9%	0.9%

Table C2: Reported Division of Childcare Tasks - Male Respondents (N = 25!!)

Task	Always Me	Usually Me	Shared Equally	Usually Partner	Always Partner
Dressing children	-	-	32.0%	40.0%	28.0%
Staying home when child is ill	-	4.0%	32.0%	32.0%	32.0%
Playing with children	-	4.0%	60.0%	16.0%	16.0%
Putting children to bed	-	4.0%	44.0%	32.0%	20.0%
Helping with homework	-	8.0%	48.0%	12.0%	24.0%

Table C3: Reported Division of Housework Tasks - Female Respondents (N = 216)

Task	Always Me	Usually Me	Shared Equally	Usually Partner	Always Partner
Laundry	45.4%	40.3%	10.7%	0.9%	0.5%
Small repairs	6.9%	10.2%	22.2%	37.5%	16.2%
Care for sick family member	19.4%	23.6%	46.8%	1.9%	0.5%
Grocery shopping	12.5%	13.0%	50.0%	16.2%	2.8%
Cleaning	41.2%	34.7%	20.4%	0.5%	0.5%
Cooking	42.1%	28.7%	18.5%	1.9%	0.5%

Table C4: Reported Division of Housework Tasks - Male Respondents (N = 25!!)

Task	Always Me	Usually Me	Shared Equally	Usually Partner	Always Partner
Laundry	-	4.0%	12.0%	48.0%	36.0%
Small repairs	20.0%	56.0%	12.0%	-	12.0%
Care for sick family member	-	16.0%	52.0%	12.0%	16.0%
Grocery shopping	-	36.0%	36.0%	4.0%	20.0%
Cleaning	-	-	16.0%	44.0%	32.0%
Cooking	4.0%	-	24.0%	32.0%	32.0%

Declaration of Originality

Hereby I confirm, Diellza Veliu, Matr. Nr. 6612384,

that this assignment is my own work and that I have only sought and used mentioned tools.

I have clearly referenced in the text and the bibliography all sources used in the work (printed sources, internet or any other source), including verbatim citations or paraphrases. I am aware of the fact that plagiarism is an attempt to deceit which, in case of recurrence, can result in a loss of test authorization. Furthermore, I confirm that neither this work nor parts of it have been previously, or concurrently, used as an exam work – neither for other courses nor within other exam processes.

Place and date Tubingen, 07.09.2025

Signature

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to be 'Diellza Veliu', written over a horizontal line.